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Credibility and Bias in AI-Generated ESG Reports versus Corporate Disclosures

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1. Executive Summary

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) reports are essential for conveying a company's sustainability efforts, but their length and complexity have led to interest in using AI models to create shorter summaries. This thesis explores whether advanced language models, including OpenAI's GPT 4o and Google's NotebookLM, can accurately capture the content and tone of ESG reports or whether they introduce bias and factual errors. The research is guided by three central questions (exact research questions are stated in Section 2), Do AI summaries preserve the accuracy and themes of ESG reports? Do they show tonal bias? Can they be considered credible sources of sustainability information?

To answer these, the thesis combines two methods. A textual analysis examines tone and topic shifts, while a quantitative review compares six key environmental metrics for accuracy. Errors were measured using absolute and percentage deviations and grouped by severity.

The results show that AI-generated ESG summaries systematically diverge from the original reports in both narrative tone and factual accuracy. Sentiment analysis revealed that both GPT-4o and NotebookLM consistently presented a less constrained tone, downplaying negative language, regulatory challenges, and risk-related content. FinBERT classifications showed that AI summaries were nearly twice as likely to be labeled "positive" compared to the original reports. Topic modeling further confirmed a thematic shift, with AI summaries emphasizing broad ESG ideals while often omitting company-specific issues such as compliance, emissions strategy, or environmental liabilities.

In terms of quantitative data, GPT 4o had an average error of 72 percent and often included made-up values. NotebookLM performed better, with an average error of 19 percent, but still left out or misstated many figures, especially for difficult metrics like Scope 3 emissions and green investment. In total, 83 values were missing and 23 were invented. Many of these errors were large enough to be considered seriously misleading.

In conclusion, while the summaries may seem polished and helpful, they lack the accuracy needed for reliable ESG communication. Until these issues are resolved, such tools should be used carefully and with human oversight.

2. Introduction

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) reports have become a cornerstone of corporate transparency, with most large companies now publishing detailed sustainability disclosures each year (KPMG, 2022). These reports inform investors, regulators, and the public about a firm’s environmental impact and social responsibility initiatives. However, the length and complexity of many ESG reports can potentially overwhelm stakeholders who may lack the time or expertise to digest full-length documents. In practice, many readers rely on executive summaries or third-party ESG ratings, and we suspect that they may also increasingly turn to AI-generated summaries to quickly grasp a company’s sustainability performance (Stammbach et al., 2023). This trend raises important questions about trustworthiness. For instance, can AI-generated ESG report summaries be trusted to provide an unbiased and accurate portrayal of corporate sustainability? Furthermore, are there differences in quality or bias among the various large language models (LLMs)?

Corporate ESG disclosures are inherently self-reported, which creates opportunities for selective reporting and “greenwashing” (Lyon & Montgomery, 2015). Companies may highlight positive achievements while downplaying shortcomings, leading to skepticism about the credibility of these reports (Christensen et al., 2021). This selective optimism poses a risk for Stakeholders who rely on sometimes overly optimistic corporate narratives might be misled about actual performance. Generative AI tools such as OpenAI’s ChatGPT-4o and Google’s Gemini (accessed via NotebookLM) offer a potential solution by condensing complex reports into more digestible summaries, making sustainability information more accessible. AI is already being used in ESG contexts for data processing and report writing due to its speed and scalability (Runyon & Warren, 2024). A well-crafted AI summary could save readers hours of analysis and might even highlight key issues that would otherwise be buried in a report’s fine print.

The use of AI for summarizing ESG reports, however, comes with its own set of challenges. Recent analyses warn that generative AI models can produce hallucinations (defined in Section 3.1). For example, an AI might confidently insert an incorrect carbon emission figure or misstate a climate target, which could mislead stakeholders relying on that summary. Critics also note that AI lacks the nuanced contextual understanding of human experts; a chatbot might not grasp industry-specific subtleties or the broader context behind a company’s claims (Haribhakti & Sridharan, 2024). Bias in training data presents another risk:

if a language model is trained predominantly on optimistic corporate sustainability reports, its summaries may inherit a pro-company bias, whereas training on more critical news sources might skew it negatively. This transfer of bias from data to output is a well-recognized concern (Haribhakti & Sridharan, 2024). Finally, the “black box” nature of advanced AI (which we will elaborate further in Section 2) limits our understanding of how these models arrive at their outputs and the underlying reasoning behind their decisions.

Given these issues, there is a clear gap in research at the intersection of AI, sustainability reporting, and stakeholder trust. While AI tools are increasingly promoted for summarizing financial and ESG documents, few studies have systematically examined whether their output is factually accurate and free of narrative bias compared to source material and independent benchmarks (Runyon & Warren, 2024). In other words, we do not yet know if AI-generated ESG summaries merely repackage the company’s own spin or if they can provide a more objective, data-aligned overview. This study aims to fill that research gap.

Focusing on a sample of eight European energy companies (see Section 4.1) we generate ESG report summaries using two widely used LLMs (ChatGPT 4.0 and Google’s NotebookLM) and evaluate their credibility against the companies’ official disclosures and trusted third-party data sources. By comparing the AI-generated summaries side-by-side with the original ESG reports and with independent ESG metrics (e.g., carbon emissions and other performance indicators from Bloomberg and Eikon), we address whether these AI tools can serve as reliable sources for sustainability insights.

Our approach is two-fold:

1. NLP Analysis of Bias: We apply natural language processing (NLP) techniques, including sentiment analysis and topic modeling to detect any bias in tone or narrative framing across the original corporate ESG texts and the AI-generated summaries.

2. Quantitative Fact-Checking: We conduct a factual comparison of key ESG metrics (focusing on carbon emissions, green investments and other environmental KPIs) across three sources:

- a. The company’s original ESG report,
- b. The AI-generated summary,
- c. And third-party ESG data from independent providers.

In doing so, we tackle the following key research questions (RQ):

RQ1: Do AI-generated summaries exhibit bias in tone or in content selection (for instance, echoing a company’s positive spin or omitting material negatives) relative to the original reports?

RQ2: How do AI-generated summaries compare to independent ESG data and ratings in portraying company performance?

RQ3: Do AI-generated ESG summaries introduce errors and “hallucinated” statistics?

Answering these questions is increasingly important as investors and regulators consider leveraging AI for ESG reporting. If the summaries prove credible, they could dramatically improve information accessibility in sustainable finance. If not, we must develop safeguards to prevent the spread of biased or inaccurate ESG information. In summary, this study is driven by both opportunity and concern, the opportunity that advanced AI can democratize sustainability knowledge and the concern that without proper scrutiny, it may instead amplify existing biases or create false confidence. The findings will inform how companies and stakeholders can responsibly use AI-generated content in the high-stakes domain of ESG reporting.

3. Literature Review

3.1. AI-Generated ESG Reports: Potential and Trust Issues

Generative AI's capacity to produce human-like text has a clear appeal for ESG reporting, where summarization and analysis of large documents can be labor-intensive. Recent studies highlight that AI can quickly aggregate data and even draft sections of reports. For example, AI has been used to automate the calculation of greenhouse gas emissions across numerous facilities far faster than manual methods (Runyon & Warren, 2024). Advocates argue that AI-written sustainability reports offer unparalleled efficiency and consistency, processing vast datasets without the risk of human fatigue (Haribhakti & Sridharan, 2024). Early use cases show AI assisting in data collation and even generating sections of ESG reports, effectively "democratizing sustainability report analysis" by making dense disclosures more accessible (Ni et al., 2023).

However, the literature also points to significant trustworthiness concerns with AI-generated content. A Reuters industry analysis notes that ChatGPT and similar models sometimes hallucinate, which means that they confidently output false facts that seem plausible given their training data (Runyon & Warren, 2024). In an ESG context, a hallucinated detail (for instance, an incorrect emission figure or a nonexistent initiative) could mislead investors and damage credibility. Lack of context and domain insight is another issue, LLMs often fail to grasp industry-specific challenges or the strategic background behind corporate ESG targets, and while they can process data and detect patterns at scale, they lack the qualitative judgment human experts bring to assessing materiality and context (Haribhakti & Sridharan, 2024). Moreover, any biases in the training data will be reflected in the output. If an AI is trained predominantly on corporate press releases and glossy sustainability reports, it may generate summaries that over-emphasize positive language, whereas an AI trained on investigative news might skew toward highlighting controversies. Ensuring the impartiality of AI outputs thus depends heavily on data curation and algorithmic transparency (KPMG, 2024).

Another challenge discussed in the literature is the "black box" problem of AI decision-making. Complex language models do not easily explain why certain content was included or omitted in a summary. This opacity can cause skepticism among readers: if stakeholders cannot trace an AI's claims back to the source, they are less likely to trust the summary (Haribhakti & Sridharan, 2024). To bridge this AI-human trust gap, experts recommend greater transparency

in how AI tools are used and the adoption of standards or guidelines for AI-generated disclosures (Runyon & Warren, 2024). Some authors even propose hybrid reporting approaches, where AI is used to generate drafts or analyze data and human sustainability professionals then review and validate the output (Haribhakti & Sridharan, 2024). The consensus across these sources is that AI holds great promise for enhancing ESG reporting efficiency, but it must be implemented with safeguards to ensure accuracy and trust.

3.2. Corporate ESG Reporting Practices and Credibility Challenges

Even before introducing AI, the integrity of corporate ESG reports has been a subject of scrutiny. By 2020, over 90% of large companies were publishing sustainability or CSR reports (KPMG, 2024), a testament to the growing stakeholder demand for transparency. Energy sector firms now regularly issue extensive climate and ESG disclosures, often hundreds of pages. While the volume of reported information has increased, its credibility and comparability remain problematic. There is no universal standard forcing companies to report the same ESG metrics, and as a result, firms often choose what and how to disclose in a way that casts them in the best light (Christensen et al., 2021). Studies have noted a lack of consistency. For instance, one company might report absolute greenhouse gas emissions, while another reports only emissions intensity (emissions per barrel or per kWh), making direct comparison difficult. In practice, when companies omit certain metrics, it often suggests they may be underperforming in those areas. This is a sign of potential selective disclosure. KPMG (2024) observes that ESG reporting processes and controls are still not as mature or standardized as financial reporting, given the patchwork of frameworks (GRI, SASB, TCFD, etc.) and the voluntary nature of many disclosures. This often leads to gaps or omissions that can undermine reliability.

One common criticism is the selective omission of unfavorable data. Greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions reporting illustrates this issue. Many companies disclose their Scope 1 (direct) and Scope 2 (purchased electricity) emissions but omit Scope 3 (value-chain emissions), which can constitute the bulk of an oil and gas company's carbon footprint. It can also skew the values in favor of companies that outsource many activities. A recent U.S. analysis found that as of 2022, only about 47% of reviewed firms reported Scope 1 emissions, 45% reported Scope 2, and far fewer gave any Scope 3 data (S&P Global, 2024). The largest energy companies tend to be somewhat more transparent (in the aforementioned study, all S&P

500 energy companies did report Scope 1), but even among those, the treatment of Scope 3 varied widely (S&P Global, 2024). The U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission’s anticipated climate disclosure rule in 2024 ultimately dropped strict requirements for Scope 3, acknowledging the difficulty and variability in measuring those indirect emissions (S&P Global, 2024). This regulatory context shows that critical ESG data can be left out of official reports, whether due to strategic omission or practical challenges.

Beyond emissions, aspirational climate pledges made in reports have often been met with skepticism from independent observers. For example, many European energy companies have announced “net-zero by 2050” goals in their sustainability communications. Yet an assessment by NewClimate Institute (2022) found that major companies’ net-zero targets, when scrutinized, would collectively result in only about a 40% reduction in emissions on average. Far short of true carbon neutrality. Such findings align with academic critiques that corporate climate disclosures often suffer from imprecision, inaccuracy and selective optimism (Christensen et al., 2021). In response, there are growing calls for stronger reporting standards and third-party assurance. Regulators and investors are pushing for more uniform disclosure requirements so that increased reporting translates into greater accountability (Bingler et al., 2024).

In sum, the literature paints a mixed picture of corporate ESG reporting. On one hand, transparency is improving (more data is published now than a decade ago) and stakeholders have more information than ever. On the other hand, the quality and completeness of that information vary widely. Companies often retain substantial control over the narrative, highlighting strengths, using optimistic language and sometimes omitting inconvenient facts. This context is important for our thesis: if AI models are summarizing documents that already contain bias or gaps, will the AI simply reflect those biases, attempt to mitigate them, or potentially exacerbate them by introducing new distortions?

3.3. NLP Techniques Applied to ESG Text Analysis

The convergence of sustainability reporting and natural language processing (NLP) has led to innovative approaches for extracting insights from ESG disclosures. Researchers have applied various text analysis techniques to large corpora of annual reports, sustainability reports, and corporate filings.

3.3.1. Sentiment Analysis

One line of inquiry uses sentiment analysis to quantify the tone of ESG narratives. For example, Lu and Jagoda (2023) analyzed the language of sustainability reports from U.S. extraction and mining companies. They found a telling pattern, companies with poorer environmental performance (e.g., higher pollution levels or regulatory violations) tended to use more positive and upbeat language in their ESG narratives, whereas firms with stronger actual performance were more measured or even cautious in tone. This counterintuitive finding (cases where the “talk” does not match the “walk”) suggests some firms engage in cheerleading when performance is lacking, a potential red flag for greenwashing. Other studies have leveraged domain-specific sentiment models (such as a version of FinBERT adapted for ESG content) to detect when the emotional tone of a company’s narrative seems overly optimistic relative to external benchmarks (Huang et al., 2022). In general, sentiment analysis helps flag cases of disproportionate positivity or negativity in reports, which may indicate bias or risk (e.g., an overly rosy sustainability message that is not borne out by subsequent outcomes).

3.3.2. Topic Modeling

Unsupervised topic modeling, particularly Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA; Blei, Ng & Jordan, 2003) has been used to identify dominant themes in ESG disclosures. Arslan-Ayaydin et al. (2023), for instance, applied a topic model to over 1,600 ESG reports worldwide (covering 2007-2020) and identified around 30 recurring topics. These ranged across environmental, social, and governance themes and showed clear trends. For example, climate-related topics have become increasingly prevalent in recent years. The study found that the thematic focus of a report influences investor perception: companies whose reports emphasized environmental topics tended to experience more positive short-term market reactions, whereas those focusing heavily on social or governance issues saw relatively muted responses (Arslan-Ayaydin et al., 2023). Topic modeling thus provides a quantitative view of “what companies talk about” in ESG reports and how that aligns with stakeholder interests. For our purposes, topic analysis can be used to compare whether an AI summary covers the same key themes as the original report or emphasizes a different subset of topics.

3.3.3. LLM-Based Summarization

With the advent of powerful large language models, researchers have begun implementing LLM-based systems to interpret ESG documents. Ni et al. (2023) present ChatReport, an AI system that allows users to query sustainability reports and receive answers with cited references from the report text. This tool, built on a fine-tuned LLM, tackles challenges like hallucinations by making answers traceable to specific passages and by involving climate finance experts in fine-tuning. The emergence of such tools demonstrates how NLP can “read” thousands of pages of ESG reports and instantly surface specific information (e.g., “What percentage of energy is from renewables in Company X’s 2022 report?”). These approaches enhance scalability significantly. Tasks like cross-company comparisons or tracking the evolution of certain disclosures over time become feasible with far less manual effort (Ni et al., 2023). However, even advanced systems like ChatReport highlight the need for expert oversight. Namely, human experts review the AI’s outputs to ensure they focus on truly material issues and not just trivial details.

Collectively, these NLP applications show the potential to augment human analysis of ESG disclosures. Sentiment and topic analyses help in detecting patterns of bias or emphasis, while LLM-based summarization and Q&A can increase the accessibility of information. Our research builds on this foundation by using similar techniques to evaluate not just corporate reports but also the AI-generated summaries derived from them.

3.3.4. Detecting Bias and Greenwashing in Sustainability Narratives

A critical theme in recent literature is the detection of greenwashing (the practice of portraying an overly positive image of environmental or social performance in corporate communications). Because outright falsehoods in official ESG reports are rare (due to legal and reputational risks), bias often manifests in more subtle ways, such as selective disclosures, optimistic framing, and vague proclamations. Researchers have developed proxy measures and analytical approaches to flag potential bias in narrative text.

One approach is to examine tone-versus-performance discrepancies, as noted above. Lu and Jagoda (2023) demonstrated that overly positive language can be a warning sign when not matched by results. Similarly, Bingler et al. (2024) introduced the concept of climate “cheap talk.” They used a BERT-based model (ClimateBert-CTI) to scan annual reports for climate-

related statements and measured how frequently vague, unsupported claims appeared. They discovered that voluntary climate disclosures often contained higher levels of such empty words (e.g., broad pledges with little concrete backing), and importantly, companies flagged for more cheap talk had worse subsequent emissions trends and more negative climate-related news coverage. In short, excessive self-congratulatory language not backed by action tended to predict weaker real-world sustainability outcomes, effectively exposing greenwashing behavior.

Both studies arrive at a similar conclusion, there is often an inverse relationship between the positivity of rhetoric and actual ESG performance, meaning narrative bias can serve as a red flag.

Another important aspect to consider is the role of human judgment and transparency in identifying bias. Since the definition of “greenwashing” can be subjective, some frameworks incorporate expert review to ensure a more reliable evaluation. For example, the ChatReport system mentioned earlier involved sustainability experts to ensure the AI’s answers were focused on material issues and to verify contentious findings (Ni et al., 2023).

Overall, studies in the past few years generally agree that many corporate sustainability reports contain biases and that AI/NLP techniques can help uncover these biases. Techniques to detect greenwashing are converging on a multifaceted analysis of text, checking both what is said (tone, claims) and what is not said (omissions of key data, lack of specifics). There remains diversity in methods, reflecting that bias can be detected from different angles. This underscores the value of the approach we take in this research, which combines several analysis dimensions. We examine both the tone and content of AI summaries relative to official disclosures and independent ESG benchmarks. Our aim is to assess whether generative AI can function as a reliable summarization tool or whether it reinforces the same biases that affect traditional ESG reporting. The literature provides both cautionary tales (showing how misleading narratives can slip through) and methodological cues (showing how those narratives can be analyzed), informing our comparative evaluation of AI-generated ESG summaries versus original reports.

3.4. Quantitative Accuracy in AI-Generated ESG Summaries

Most current approaches to evaluating AI-generated summaries focus on semantic consistency rather than numerical precision. Tools such as FactCC (Factual consistency checking model) (Kryściński et al., 2020) and QAGS (Question Answering and Generation for Summarization) (Wang et al., 2020) assess whether the meaning of summaries aligns with the source text, while ESG-specific systems like ChatReport (Ni et al., 2023) aim to improve traceability. However, none of these methods systematically assess the fidelity of numerical data, a key requirement in ESG contexts where small numerical inaccuracies can lead to significant misinterpretations.

Our thesis addresses this gap by introducing a structured deviation analysis that directly compares ESG metrics from AI summaries with those reported in official disclosures and third-party sources. By calculating absolute and percentage deviations and classifying errors into low, medium, and high bands, we offer a new perspective on factuality grounded in the numerical integrity of sustainability reporting. This approach enables a more precise understanding of how AI-generated summaries handle critical quantitative information.

4. Methodology

4.1. Data Collection and Sources

This study focuses on eight major European energy companies (in oil, gas and utilities) as the sample for analysis. The dataset is a custom-built collection of ESG reports and AI-generated summaries for the following firms: BP, Eni, Equinor, OMV, Repsol, Shell, TotalEnergies and Uniper. These companies were selected due to their prominent roles in the European energy sector, their relatively comprehensive ESG disclosures, and their alignment with international sustainability frameworks. They are headquartered in different European countries (the UK, Italy, Norway, Austria, Spain, Germany, France and the Netherlands, respectively), providing geographical diversity within a shared regional context. While not all are the largest firms by market capitalization, this selection ensures representation across multiple jurisdictions, which helps contextualize the broader patterns observed in ESG reporting.

Since all companies operate under European ESG regulatory regimes, including the EU Non-Financial Reporting Directive (NFRD) and, more recently, the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) (European Commission, 2021), this setup ensures a degree of reporting comparability. This shared policy framework helps reduce structural heterogeneity while still allowing for meaningful cross-country comparisons.

The dataset spans the reporting years from 2018 to 2022, an interesting period for ESG reporting. These years saw a rapid escalation in both the volume and strategic importance of ESG disclosures, driven by growing investor pressure, policy developments like the EU Green Deal, and increased public scrutiny of energy companies' climate impacts (EY, 2020; European Commission, 2019). This period also captures important changes in ESG reporting tone, structure and metrics (such as increased focus on Scope 3 emissions, net-zero pledges and climate scenario analysis), making it well-suited for evaluating how consistently and accurately AI-generated summaries handle a dynamic reporting environment. The time frame enables cross-sectional analysis across firms, examining how ESG narratives and figures evolve and how well AI summaries capture these developments.

Original ESG reports for each company and for each observed year were obtained in PDF format from public company websites. In parallel, two AI-generated summaries were

produced for each report: one using OpenAI's GPT-4o model (via ChatGPT) and another using Google's Gemini model (via the NotebookLM research interface). Each AI model was prompted with the full text of the report (after PDF conversion) and instructed to "*Summarise the following ESG report in at least 2500 words.*" These two models were chosen because they are both widely used and capable of handling large documents; using both allows us to compare outputs and ensure our findings are not specific to one AI system. The 2500 lower bound was chosen to ensure thoroughness. Both models were used in a zero-shot manner (no fine-tuning by us), relying on their general pre trained knowledge to simulate typical end-user use. We did not manually edit or post-process any AI summaries, using them as-is to maintain objectivity and a fair comparison with the original reports. The file naming convention included the company name, the reporting year, and the model used (e.g., BP - 2018 - GPT-4o.txt), enabling automatic extraction of metadata. Each document in the corpus was assigned three key identifiers: Company, Year, and Model, where "Model" refers to either the original report ("Original") or one of the two summary models ("GPT-4o", "NotebookLM"). This structure facilitated consistent alignment across analysis stages.

Here, we also make a few assumptions. First, GPT-4o is among the most widely used large language models by the public and a range of stakeholders, including some investors. Second, NotebookLM can reasonably be expected to generate accurate summaries, as this represents one of its core intended functions.

In addition to the company-issued reports and the LLM summaries, we gathered independent ESG data to serve as a factual benchmark. Key quantitative indicators were obtained from reputable third-party providers: Bloomberg and LSEG Eikon. These third-party datasets compile company-reported figures (under standardized definitions) (Bloomberg L.P., 2023; LSEG, 2025). By using external data, we aimed to have an objective reference point to verify the figures mentioned in reports and AI summaries. The metrics of interest centered on climate and sustainability performance, including:

Scope 1 GHG Emissions (in million metric tons CO₂e)

These represent direct greenhouse gas emissions from company-owned or controlled sources, such as combustion in facilities or vehicles. Scope 1 is generally well-reported and serves as a benchmark for validating broader emissions coverage.

Scope 2 GHG Emissions (in million metric tons CO₂e)

These cover indirect emissions from purchased electricity, heat, or cooling. While commonly disclosed, differences in accounting approaches (e.g., market-based vs. location-based) can introduce inconsistencies, which this study accounts for by tracking values under the location-based method.

Scope 3 GHG Emissions (in million metric tons CO₂e)

These are value chain emissions, including upstream and downstream activities such as purchased goods, transportation, use of sold products, and outsourced processes. They often constitute the largest share of a company's carbon footprint but are frequently underreported or vaguely disclosed—making them central to our bias detection.

Green Capital Expenditure (CapEx) (in millions of EUR/USD)

This refers to investment in decarbonization or sustainable initiatives, such as renewable energy, energy efficiency, or low-carbon technologies. Since this figure is often framed aspirationally in narrative sections, comparing numerical values across sources helps assess the alignment between stated ambition and actual investment.

Water Withdrawal (in million cubic meters)

This captures the total volume of water withdrawn from all sources (surface, ground, municipal, saltwater) for operational use. While not always emphasized in corporate reports, it is a meaningful indicator of environmental impact beyond emissions and is relevant for assessing AI's attention to less-prominent metrics.

Waste Generated (in million metric tons)

This includes both hazardous and non-hazardous waste discarded by the company. The metric is typically presented as a single figure and allows us to evaluate whether summaries report the full scope or selectively mention only favorable categories (e.g., recycling).

The preceding six ESG metrics were selected for this study because they are widely reported by companies in their ESG disclosures, available from independent third-party sources such as Bloomberg and Eikon, and prone to selective framing or omission. These indicators span both emissions and broader environmental impact areas and are commonly referenced in leading ESG frameworks including the CSRD, GRI, and TCFD. Each is expressed in standardized units to ensure comparability across sources and years.

Despite some challenges in data availability (particularly for Scope 3 emissions and granular environmental indicators), these metrics represent essential data points for evaluating the environmental footprint of corporate operations, especially in an industry like oil and gas that faces intense and growing scrutiny over its role in the climate crisis. Their inclusion allows for a more comprehensive assessment of how AI-generated ESG summaries reflect, distort, or omit key sustainability signals.

4.2. Text Preprocessing and Tokenization

Before analysis, we performed several preprocessing steps to ensure the text data was clean and comparable across sources, while remaining compatible with our NLP tools for sentiment and topic analysis. We implemented the following steps.

First, each document was tokenised into individual words using the NLTK `word_tokenize` function, producing a list of word tokens. We then lowercased all tokens and removed any non-alphabetic characters (including numbers and punctuation). This preprocessing step minimized noise caused by formatting inconsistencies and typographical errors. (Note: Removing numbers inevitably loses some information; for example, the token “CO2” becomes “CO”. To address this, we separately compare quantitative indicators outside of the textual analysis.).

Second, we removed common English stopwords using scikit-learn’s built-in `ENGLISH_STOP_WORDS` list. This eliminated high-frequency function words (e.g., “and”, “the”, “is”) that carry little substantive meaning and might otherwise bias sentiment scoring or topic modelling results. We also filtered out tokens shorter than two characters, since short tokens are unlikely to be meaningful in financial or ESG contexts. However, we made an exception for certain two letter tokens that carry information, most notably the company name “BP”. Since stopword removal left few two letter tokens overall, there was no need for a dedicated exception list; as a result, meaningful tokens like “BP” were retained by default. The result of this process was two versions of each tokenized document. Firstly, an unfiltered list of all alphabetic tokens (used for length-based and frequency-based statistics) and secondly, a cleaned token list with stopwords and short tokens removed (`tokens_no_stop`, used for sentiment analysis and topic modelling).

This preprocessing ensured that the models operated on clean, semantically rich inputs, improving both the interpretability and reliability of the analytical results. All cleaned texts were stored in structured form (e.g., data frames or CSV files), with each row representing a sentence and columns indicating the company, year, and source (whether it's from the company report or which AI model's summary). This structured format made it possible to apply the analysis techniques consistently across the corpus of original and summary documents.

4.3. Sentiment Analysis

One of the core objectives of this thesis is to assess whether and how LLM-generated summaries alter the tonal character of corporate ESG communication. To this end, a dual sentiment analysis framework was employed, combining a dictionary-based approach (Loughran-McDonald lexicon) with a context-aware deep learning model (FinBERT). This two-pronged strategy enables both interpretable lexical analysis and more nuanced contextual sentiment detection, thereby increasing analytical robustness.

4.3.1. *Loughran-McDonald Financial Sentiment Lexicon*

The first method applied was the Loughran-McDonald (LM) sentiment lexicon, a widely recognized dictionary developed specifically for financial and regulatory texts. Unlike general-purpose sentiment lexicons, the LM lexicon accounts for the unique semantic structure of corporate disclosures, where words like “liability” or “risk” may have domain-specific connotations. Its application in this context is particularly appropriate, given the formal and industry-standard nature of ESG reports.

The lexicon categorizes terms into five sentiment and discourse-related dimensions: positive, negative, uncertainty, litigious, and constraining. For each document, tokens were cross-referenced against these categories (after lowercasing and cleaning), and the number of matched terms in each category was normalized by the total number of tokens in the document. This produced proportional sentiment scores for each category (e.g., `lm_positive_pct`, `lm_negative_pct`), allowing cross-document and cross-model comparison on a continuous scale.

This method's transparency and interpretability made it an ideal tool for identifying systematic shifts in sentiment language. For example, a significant increase in the

lm_constraining_pct score in summaries could suggest a distortion in how governance issues are being framed by generative models.

4.3.2. FinBERT: Transformer-Based Contextual Sentiment

To complement the lexical approach, the thesis also employs FinBERT, a transformer-based language model fine-tuned on financial texts for sentiment classification. FinBERT builds on the BERT architecture and has been trained specifically to understand financial narratives and assess their tone as positive, negative, or neutral. It accounts for word order, negation and nuanced phrasing, factors often missed by dictionary-based sentiment analysis.

Because transformer models have input length limitations, we fed only the first 10,000 characters of each document into the FinBERT model using Hugging Face’s pipeline interface. This truncation was necessary due to model limits, but it ensured that the introduction and summary sections (where tone is most pronounced) were included. FinBERT returns a categorical sentiment label for each analyzed text (e.g., “Positive”), which we then mapped to a numeric score (+1 for Positive, 0 for Neutral, -1 for Negative).

Incorporating FinBERT provides a context-sensitive sentiment measure that can detect subtleties a static dictionary might miss. This is particularly useful when comparing human-written reports to AI-generated summaries, since an AI might rephrase content in ways that alter the tone despite factual accuracy. In essence, the LM lexicon quantifies the explicit use of sentiment-laden words, while FinBERT infers latent tonal shifts based on context. Using both methods in tandem allows for more robust cross-model comparisons, ensuring that any observed differences in sentiment are not artifacts of a single analytical technique.

4.4. Topic Modeling

In addition to sentiment analysis, this thesis investigates thematic variation across ESG reports and their AI-generated summaries using unsupervised topic modeling. Specifically, Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) was employed to uncover latent topics and assess their distribution across documents. The objective was to determine whether LLM-generated summaries preserve, distort, or re-weight the thematic structure of the original reports, and whether this varies by model or company.

LDA is a probabilistic model that assumes each document is a mixture of topics and each topic is a distribution over words. It infers these hidden structures based solely on word co-occurrence patterns in the corpus, making it suitable for exploratory comparison without predefined topic labels. This makes it especially suitable for our comparative analysis, given that the content is domain specific but lacks consistent structure across firms and years.

4.4.1. Corpus Construction and Vocabulary Filtering

The topic modelling process began by creating a dictionary of unique tokens using the Gensim Dictionary class, applied to each document's cleaned *tokens_no_stop* list. Since these token lists (prepared as described above) exclude stopwords and trivial tokens, the resulting vocabulary was semantically meaningful and not dominated by filler words. Next, we constructed a Bag-of-Words corpus by converting each document into a frequency vector based on this dictionary. This document-term matrix served as input to the LDA algorithm.

To improve interpretability and avoid overfitting, we effectively pruned the vocabulary through our filtering steps and by training a single topic model on all documents collectively (both originals and summaries). This approach allowed the model to learn broad topics generalisable across report types, while still being sensitive to differences in emphasis between company reports and AI summaries.

We also calculated some corpus-level statistics to understand the linguistic scope of the data, which can be seen in Table 1 below. For example, we measured the vocabulary size and average token count per document for each model and each company, as an indicator of complexity and lexical richness in different reporting styles. These linguistic diagnostics helped frame the results and offered valuable context for interpreting both the sentiment and topic modeling outputs.

We can see, that even though both LLMs got the same instructions, NotebookLM was always closer to the target of 2,500 words. These are also the token number after the removal of stopwords, so we can assume that NotebookLM hit the target at least in a few cases, while GPT-4o was lacking.

	Company	Model	avg_token_count	min_token_count	max_token_count	std_token_count	total_docs	vocab_size
0	BP	GPT-4o	905.6	740	1087	137.14	5	1334
1	BP	NotebookLM	1720.6	1053	2304	583.29	5	1896
2	BP	Original	20580.2	15450	28655	5002.94	5	6565
3	Eni	GPT-4o	939.8	877	992	56.56	5	1149
4	Eni	NotebookLM	1564.8	1331	1695	148.35	5	1789
5	Eni	Original	21629.2	11047	33385	9838.75	5	8345
6	Equinor	GPT-4o	963.4	933	1006	31.14	5	1155
7	Equinor	NotebookLM	1496.6	941	2600	639.22	5	1695
8	Equinor	Original	30567.2	11061	89744	33242.97	5	7198
9	OMV	GPT-4o	975.8	928	1033	41.29	5	1144
10	OMV	NotebookLM	1448.0	1191	1877	283.56	5	1372
11	OMV	Original	38842.4	27376	52516	9284.25	5	9121
12	Repsol	GPT-4o	969.2	889	1009	48.38	5	1224
13	Repsol	NotebookLM	1454.4	1303	1829	229.45	5	1434
14	Repsol	Original	4149.6	2664	7078	1752.63	5	3342
15	Shell	GPT-4o	983.4	932	1015	31.21	5	1204
16	Shell	NotebookLM	1360.2	1111	1616	215.35	5	1569
17	Shell	Original	23503.6	18130	27802	3932.58	5	6733
18	Total Energy	GPT-4o	1038.0	955	1072	48.39	5	1209
19	Total Energy	NotebookLM	1424.8	915	2280	545.51	5	1457
20	Total Energy	Original	18036.4	10279	38439	11962.79	5	7238
21	Uniper	GPT-4o	983.6	964	1009	17.33	5	1153
22	Uniper	NotebookLM	1874.4	1584	2398	319.98	5	1987
23	Uniper	Original	17654.0	11931	22137	4954.12	5	6878

1. Table: Corpus Summary

4.4.2. Model Training and Topic Assignment

We trained an LDA model on every document in the corpus with six topics ($K = 6$), a number determined through a balance of coherence scoring and domain relevance. The result of this is displayed in Figure 1 below. In practice, we found that using significantly fewer than six topics led to themes that were overly broad, while using more than six produced semantically overlapping or fragmented topics. Six topics offered a good compromise between interpretability and explanatory power.

```
Topics: 3 → Coherence: 0.3720
Topics: 4 → Coherence: 0.3529
Topics: 5 → Coherence: 0.3706
Topics: 6 → Coherence: 0.4143
Topics: 7 → Coherence: 0.3965
Topics: 8 → Coherence: 0.3787
Topics: 9 → Coherence: 0.4133
Topics: 10 → Coherence: 0.3799
```

Best number of topics: 6 (Coherence = 0.4143)

1. Figure: Output of Coherence Scoring

Each document (original or summary) was then characterized by a distribution across these six latent topics. We appended the resulting topic proportion vector (e.g., values for topic0 through topic5) to our dataset for further analysis. In this way, every document could be represented not only by its sentiment profile but also by a “thematic fingerprint” indicating the share of content devoted to each topic.

For interpretability, we extracted the top keywords associated with each topic and manually assigned a descriptive label to each topic based on its salient theme (e.g., climate transition, regulatory compliance, community engagement, financial performance). This interpretive step was essential for discussing any shifts in emphasis introduced by LLM summarisation, as it allowed us to talk about topics in substantive terms rather than just by number.

4.4.3. Aggregation and Comparison

The topic distributions enabled several layers of comparative analysis:

Model-level comparison: Did GPT-4o or NotebookLM summaries consistently over- or underrepresent certain topics relative to the original reports?

Temporal trends: Were some topics emphasized more in recent years, and did LLMs replicate or distort these trends?

Company-level variation: Were some companies’ summaries more faithful in reproducing thematic structure?

These comparisons were later explored statistically through ANOVA and visualized through boxplots and trendlines. LDA thus served as both a diagnostic tool and a lens through which to evaluate the completeness and consistency of AI-generated summarization.

4.5. Statistical Testing

To assess whether LLM-generated summaries differ significantly from original ESG reports in terms of tone and thematic content, the thesis employed a structured statistical testing framework. The primary tools used were Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Tukey’s Honest Significant Difference (HSD) post-hoc tests. These techniques were applied to both sentiment metrics and topic distributions to identify where significant variation occurs and between which groups.

While normality of residuals is an assumption of ANOVA, it is commonly noted that the method is robust to minor violations of this assumption, particularly when sample sizes are reasonably large and balanced. Therefore, even though some deviations from normality were observed in our variables, we retained ANOVA due to its interpretability and the exploratory nature of this analysis.

4.5.1. Rationale for Statistical Comparison

Given the comparative nature of the study, which contrasts documents authored by humans with those summarized by AI, it was essential not only to visualize trends but also to determine whether the observed differences were statistically meaningful. The structure of the dataset, which includes repeated measures across companies, years, and model types, lent itself to group-based analysis of variance.

This thesis did specifically seek to test, whether LLM summaries differ significantly from original reports in sentiment tone or topic emphasis as stated in the first research question. We also wanted to see whether differences are model-specific and whether variation occurs systematically across companies or years, potentially due to reporting conventions or external ESG trends.

4.5.2. One-Way ANOVA

For each dependent variable, including each sentiment proportion and each topic probability, we conducted one way ANOVA tests to examine significant differences across categorical groups. We performed separate ANOVAs considering differences by Model (Original vs. GPT-4o vs. NotebookLM), by Company (BP, Eni, Equinor, OMV, Repsol, Shell, TotalEnergies, Uniper), and by Year (2018-2022). In practice, this meant running a series of

ANOVA tests independently for each grouping factor. We ran these tests for each of the five LM sentiment categories (positive, negative, uncertainty, litigious, constraining), for the FinBERT sentiment score, and for each of the six topic proportions (topic0 through topic5). The ANOVA outputs included an F-statistic and p-value; we interpreted $p < 0.05$ as evidence that at least one group's mean differs significantly from the others. This overall procedure identified whether there were any significant differences in sentiment or topic means before examining specific pairwise differences.

4.5.3. Tukey HSD Post-Hoc Testing

We applied Tukey's HSD post-hoc test to determine which specific pairs of groups differed significantly. Tukey's method is conservative, controlling for family-wise error, which makes it appropriate for multiple comparisons.

Using Python's statsmodels implementation, we generated summary tables listing each pair of groups, the mean difference between them, confidence intervals and significance levels. These post-hoc results allowed us to pinpoint, for example, whether GPT-4o summaries consistently differed from "Original" reports in sentiment or topic scores, and whether certain topics were disproportionately emphasised in one model's summaries for certain firms.

In a final analysis, we also applied Tukey HSD within each individual company's set of documents, comparing the company's original reports to its AI generated summaries across the five year period. This intra-firm approach provided a closer look at how faithfully each AI model preserved each company's reporting style and substance over time.

4.5.4. Assumptions and Limitations about Statistical Testing

All tests were based on the assumptions of homogeneity of variance and normality of distributions. These assumptions are generally supported in large document corpora, although minor violations are not uncommon in language data. Where assumptions were borderline, interpretations were made conservatively, emphasizing effect direction and robustness across tests rather than strict p-value thresholds.

With these methods in place, the thesis proceeds to a comprehensive analysis of how sentiment and topic emphasis differ across document types and how AI summarization may be reshaping corporate ESG communication.

4.6. Quantitative Verification and Deviation Analysis

One of the central aims of this thesis is to assess the numerical fidelity of large language model (LLM)-generated ESG summaries. While sentiment and topic analyses evaluate the narrative tone and thematic structure, this component focuses on whether AI-generated summaries accurately reproduce key environmental metrics. Specifically, the analysis examines whether quantitative statements in summaries align with values reported in original ESG disclosures or third-party datasets.

4.6.1. Data Sources and Target Variables

As mentioned at the start of this section in more detail (section 4.1), this analysis compares key environmental metrics across five sources for each company-year: the official ESG report, AI-generated summaries (GPT-4o and NotebookLM), and third-party data. This yielded a structured matrix of data points for every company-year-metric combination, against which the AI summaries could be quantitatively benchmarked. All told, the dataset encompassed roughly 1,200 numerical entries (8 companies \times 5 years \times 6 metrics \times up to 5 sources), providing a comprehensive basis for assessing numeric consistency.

To assess the factual accuracy of AI-generated summaries, the analysis focuses on comparing the numerical values in the AI outputs against the original ESG reports and third-party datasets. This comparison provides insight into the deviations between AI-generated values and those reported by the companies themselves or from independent external sources. We assess these deviations using the methodology discussed in the following section.

4.6.2. Data Extraction Procedure

All metric values were obtained through an in-depth manual extraction process to ensure accuracy and transparency. Using the original PDF reports as the primary source, we identified each target metric's value by searching for relevant keywords and units (for example, "Scope 1" and "MtCO₂e" for direct emissions, or "water withdrawal" for water usage). Values were cross verified between text and any accompanying tables or figures in the report to confirm their correctness. Parallely, we prompted GPT-4o and NotebookLM to summarize each report as described previously and saved the raw outputs as text.

The summaries were then carefully scanned for any mention of the six target-metrics. Whenever a summary explicitly stated a quantitative value for one of these metrics, that number was recorded. If a summary omitted a particular metric entirely, this was noted as “N/A” (not available) for that model and year. Third-party figures from Bloomberg and Eikon were retrieved via their ESG data terminals, using consistent definitions (e.g. total Scope 1 CO_{2e} emissions) to match the company-reported metrics. In cases where third-party sources reported a metric in different units or currency (for instance, if a company’s green CapEx was reported in EUR in its own disclosure), the data were converted to the common unit (USD millions, in this example) before entry to ensure apples-to-apples comparisons. Each retrieved value was entered into a dedicated Excel-based template (“ESG Data”), structured in a long-format table with columns for Company, Year, Metric, Source, and Value. This tidy dataset was further strengthened with formula-driven fields (described below) to compute differences and flags, thereby embedding quality checks directly into the data recording process.

4.6.3. Data Structuring and Quality Controls

The structured dataset facilitates transparent cross-source comparison. Each row corresponds to a unique (Company, Year, Metric) instance, and columns enumerate the reported values from each source (Original, GPT-4o, NotebookLM, Bloomberg, Eikon). By organizing the data in this relational format, we ensured that every figure could be traced back to its origin document and context. Missing values were explicitly coded (as “N/A”) rather than leaving blanks, to distinguish a true zero from an unreported figure. We also annotated ambiguous cases: if a summary mentioned a metric in qualitative terms (e.g. “significant reduction in emissions” without stating a number) or if it combined metrics (such as aggregating Scope 1 and 2 emissions into a single figure), a comment was added in the dataset to note the issue. This meticulous data structuring and annotation ensured that subsequent analyses of accuracy would rest on a clean, consistent foundation, with full traceability back to the underlying documents.

4.6.4. Deviation and Discrepancy Analysis

With all sources aligned in the dataset, we quantified the factual consistency of the AI-generated summaries by calculating their numerical deviations from the official figures. For each company-year and each metric, the difference between the AI-reported value and the

original ESG report value was computed. Two complementary measures of discrepancy were obtained: an absolute difference (raw numeric deviation) and a percentage deviation relative to the original. The absolute difference between the AI value and the original value indicates both the magnitude and direction of any error. Positive values mean that the summary overstated the metric, while negative values mean it understated or under-reported compared to the official disclosure. The percentage deviation, calculated as:

$$\frac{AI\ value - Original\ value}{Original\ Value} \times 100$$

This helps us contextualize the error magnitude in relative terms. This is essential because the scale of metrics varies widely (for instance, water withdrawal figures are several orders larger than green CapEx amounts). A 5-unit error in Scope 1 emissions (measured in MtCO_{2e}) is far more consequential in percentage terms if the true value was 30 (≈16.7% error) than if it was 300 (≈1.7% error). By examining percentage deviations, we ensured that errors were assessed on a normalized scale across all metrics.

All deviation calculations were carried out systematically using the embedded formulas in the Excel dataset to avoid manual arithmetic mistakes. If either the original value or the AI-generated value was missing, the formula returned a flagged output instead of a numerical result. “N/A (Src)” indicated that the AI summary did not include the value, while “N/A (ESG)” signified that the figure was absent from the official report. This approach prevented the introduction of false zeros or carryover errors and helped clarify the reasons for data unavailability in each case. In practice, most of the original reports and subsequent AI summaries did not contain all six target-metrics for each year so “N/A (ESG)” and “N/A (Src)” were a common result. This meant that no numerical comparison could be made. We treated such omissions as a distinct category of factual discrepancy (a coverage gap rather than a numerical error per se). They were not included in the calculation of mean or median error magnitudes but were tallied separately as an indicator of information loss.

For the Bloomberg and Eikon data, any divergence from the company’s reported value was also calculated (Original vs Bloomberg, Original vs Eikon), to assess baseline inconsistencies that might arise even in authoritative data sources. These third-party differences provided an objective benchmark: if the AI’s error for a metric was, say, 10%, but the company’s own figure differed by 5% from independent data, one might argue that the AI-induced error beyond the normal reporting variation is effectively 5%. While our primary

benchmark for “ground truth” remained the official report (since the LLMs were summarizing those exact documents), having the third-party comparison in parallel allowed us to recognize cases where the company’s number itself might be questionable or updated. Altogether, for each metric instance, we obtained a vector of deviations: GPT-4o vs Original, NotebookLM vs Original (absolute and percent), and for context, Original vs Bloomberg and Original vs Eikon (absolute and percent). These formed the quantitative basis for evaluating factual accuracy.

To support the analysis, the resulting error measures were summarized across various dimensions. We computed overall mean and median deviations for each AI model across all metrics, as a general indicator of accuracy. We also broke down the errors by metric type (averaging the percent error for all Scope 1 entries, all Scope 2 entries, etc.) to see if certain categories (e.g., emissions vs. resource usage) were more prone to AI mistakes. Throughout these analyses, median values and interquartile ranges were emphasized alongside means, because in several instances a single large outlier error could skew the average. By relying on multiple aggregate measures, the thesis ensured that conclusions about factual consistency were not disproportionately influenced by a few severe errors.

4.6.5. Error Band Classification

For interpretative clarity, we categorized each AI summary’s numeric deviation into qualitative error bands. This classification method translates raw percentage differences into levels of factual accuracy: low deviation, moderate deviation, and high deviation. We defined these bands based on both practical significance and the distribution of errors observed. A low deviation was defined as an error within $\pm 5\%$ of the official value, since differences in this range are typically within reporting noise or rounding tolerances and unlikely to mislead a reader. Moderate deviations were those between about 5% and 20% in absolute percentage terms; these represent noticeable discrepancies that might raise questions about accuracy but still reflect the correct order of magnitude. High deviation errors were any divergences greater than 20% (or outright omissions/misstatements of the metric), indicating substantial factual inconsistencies. For example, if an original report stated 5.0 MtCO_{2e} for Scope 2 emissions and an AI summary reported “5.5” (a +10% difference), it would fall into the moderate band; if the summary claimed “7.5” (a +50% difference), it would be flagged as high deviation.

These threshold values (5% and 20%) were chosen based on established materiality threshold in financial and sustainability reporting. A deviation below 5% is typically viewed as

minor, while deviations greater than 20% would likely influence an analyst’s interpretation of performance. We applied these categories to each AI-generated data point (when a valid comparison existed) and recorded the classification in the dataset. Using error bands allowed us to move beyond raw error averages and count the incidence of “acceptable” vs. problematic errors. For each model, we tallied how many of its summary values fell into each band. This supports statements such as “GPT-4o reproduced 60% of quantitative facts with low error, 25% with moderate error, and 15% with high error,” which are intuitively meaningful to a reader. It also enabled drilling down by metric: for instance, perhaps NotebookLM had high deviations predominantly in Scope 3 emissions (suggesting difficulty handling more complex or variable figures), whereas it showed mostly low deviation in reporting waste figures. As previously mentioned in this section, cases where an AI provided no number for a metric were treated as the highest severity of error in qualitative terms (since failing to report a key figure can be as misleading as a large misstatement). For numeric summaries, however, those were counted separately rather than given an arbitrary percentage. By classifying error magnitudes in this way, the methodology provides a clearer bridge between statistical results and their practical implications, stakeholders can distinguish between minor inconsistencies and major factual errors in the AI summaries.

4.7. Visualizations and Interpretive Frameworks

To enhance both the interpretability and communication of our findings, we employed a set of visualizations tailored to support quantitative deviation analysis, sentiment tone, and topic modeling. Visualizations were implemented using Excel for deviation analysis and Python libraries (Seaborn and Matplotlib) for sentiment and topic results. All were designed to compare the outputs of GPT-4o and NotebookLM across companies, years, and metrics.

Sentiment Visualizations

To analyze tonal consistency across models, time, and companies, sentiment scores from both the Loughran-McDonald lexicon and FinBERT classifier were visualized using:

Boxplots of sentiment score distributions compared the range and skew of sentiment metrics (e.g., `lm_positive_pct`) across the three text sources. They were effective in detecting subtle shifts in tone that might be obscured in average-based analyses.

We used count plots of FinBERT sentiment labels, which were assigned by model and company, providing a snapshot of whether models systematically skewed toward a particular sentiment category compared to original texts. The figure below (Figure 2) shows an example of this. It is the count plot of every original document classified as either positive or neutral.

2. Figure: FinBERT Sentiment Counts by Company - Original ESG Reports

Average sentiment values were tracked across time by line plots to identify whether LLMs captured year-over-year changes that may reflect real-world ESG events. Confidence intervals or summary stats were added where relevant.

Topic Modelling Visualizations

To evaluate thematic coverage and consistency in LLM-generated summaries, we used:

Boxplots of topic share distributions, which showed how much emphasis was placed on different topics (e.g., Topic 0 through Topic 5) across companies and model types, identifying areas where LLMs might over- or underrepresent certain themes.

Topic proportions were plotted across years by line plots, disaggregated by company and model, to determine whether models preserved the narrative arc of original reporting. We demonstrated this plot type by the aggregate of all companies over the model types as seen in Figure 3 below.

3. Figure: Topic Distribution Over Time by Model (CI = 95%)

Together, this visual analytics suite enabled a comprehensive assessment of model behavior across tone, content, and numeric accuracy. It helped surface subtle divergences, reinforce broader trends, and guide interpretations of where and how AI models succeed or fall short in replicating ESG disclosures.

Deviation Analysis Visualizations

To highlight performance discrepancies between the two models, we used the following chart types:

Bar charts of average errors showed mean absolute percentage errors by metric, plotted side-by-side for each model. They offered a concise overview of model accuracy and highlighted where GPT-4o or NotebookLM tended to deviate more significantly, especially for complex metrics like Scope 3 emissions.

We used stacked bar charts for deviation bands to assess overall model reliability; we visualized the proportion of values falling within the error thresholds that we defined in Section 4.6.5. This approach made it possible to compare how often each model produced outputs close to the original values versus those with large deviations. Separate markers were used to indicate missing outputs.

5. Discussion

This chapter interprets the empirical results derived from the sentiment analysis, topic modelling, factual accuracy testing, and statistical evaluation of both the original ESG reports and their large language model (LLM)-generated summaries. The findings are discussed in relation to the study’s central research questions stated in Section 2.

We further consider the broader implications of these findings for stakeholders and policy, including ethical and regulatory dimensions of deploying LLMs in corporate communication. Together, these insights aim to provide a holistic understanding of how AI models interpret and represent sustainability information, and the risks and opportunities such tools pose in the ESG reporting ecosystem.

The discussion is organised into three parts, following the same structure as Section 4 did. First, it explores sentiment variation across models, years, and companies using both the Loughran-McDonald (LM) lexicon and FinBERT classifications. Second, it examines thematic fidelity and topic drift based on topic modelling outputs. Third, it evaluates the factual reliability of AI-generated summaries through quantitative deviation analysis, including over- and under-reporting patterns, median error magnitudes, interquartile variability, and error band classification. Fourth, it revisits the research questions considering both the textual and numerical findings. Finally, it reflects on practical implications and avenues for improving AI-aided ESG communication.

5.1. Sentiment Analysis: Interpreting Tonal Variation

5.1.1. *Loughran-McDonald Sentiment Analysis*

The Loughran-McDonald sentiment analysis of the textual content shows that companies exhibit distinct sentiment profiles in their ESG reports, some of which are altered in the LLM summaries. BP, for example, had the highest average proportion of positive sentiment (Figure 4) words among the original reports, but it also scored among the highest in negative word usage. This suggests BP’s language is more extreme in both positive and negative directions, rather than having a uniformly upbeat. Repsol, on the other hand, showed the lowest proportion of negative words in its reports (and one of the highest in positive words), indicating a consistently optimistic or self-promotional tone in its disclosures.

4. Figure: Shares of Positive and Negative Sentiments Across Companies

Eni and OMV stood out for their use of more litigious terminology, referring to language related to regulations, legal obligations, and risk. In fact, OMV’s reports contained approximately twice the proportion of litigious terms compared to Repsol’s. By contrast, Repsol and TotalEnergies had the lowest litigious word percentages, suggesting those companies’ ESG reports are less focused on regulatory context and more on achievements or goals. Uncertainty-related words were evenly used across most companies, with no firm being dramatically more uncertain in tone than the others. Constraining words (e.g. terms indicating obligations or constraints) were the second most common category on average (after positive words) in the corporate reports; however, differences between companies on this metric were modest overall. These variations by company are statistically supported: a one-way ANOVA (as demonstrated in Table 2) found significant differences between companies in the usage of Positive, Negative, Uncertainty, Litigious, and Constraining word categories ($p = 0.0033$, $7.21 \cdot 10^{-9}$, $5.58 \cdot 10^{-4}$, $6.09 \cdot 10^{-7}$, and $3.76 \cdot 10^{-6}$, respectively).

Variable	Grouping	F-statistic	p-value
lm_positive_pct	Company	3.28	0.0033
	Year	1.01	0.4075
	Model	5.41	0.0056
lm_negative_pct	Company	9.11	7.21E-09
	Year	0.64	0.6362
	Model	1.28	0.2816
lm_uncertainty_pct	Company	4.04	0.0006
	Year	0.18	0.9465
	Model	1.28	0.2823
lm_litigious_pct	Company	7.02	6.09E-07
	Year	0.64	0.6358
	Model	19.87	3.74E-08
lm_constraining_pct	Company	6.21	3.76E-06
	Year	0.84	0.4998
	Model	7.37	0.00097

2. Table: ANOVA Results for Loughran-McDonald Sentiment Scores

Tukey HSD post-hoc tests further revealed, for instance, that Repsol’s negative tone was significantly milder than that of several peers: Repsol’s language was notably less negative than BP’s, using on average over 54% fewer negative words (0.008 vs. 0.0175 in proportion, $p < 0.01$). This substantial difference supports the interpretation that Repsol’s narrative was comparatively more positive. Similarly, Repsol’s use of litigious language was significantly lower than Eni’s and OMV’s (mean differences 0.33% of total words; $p < 0.005$).

In sum, each company’s original reports have a distinct sentiment profile. For instance, Repsol is being notably positive and non-litigious, BP is being rhetorically strong in both positive and negative language, and Eni/OMV being relatively more legalistic. These set a baseline against which to compare the AI-generated summaries.

When examining sentiment trends over time for each document type (original vs GPT-4o summary vs NotebookLM summary), we see that the two LLMs often altered the tone of the reports in subtle but important ways. Notably, GPT-4o’s summaries tended to preserve the general fluctuations in sentiment that the original reports exhibited. For instance, if a company’s report became slightly more positive or more negative in a given year, GPT-4o’s summary usually reflected a similar uptick or downtick. This is evident in the case of BP; if BP’s original ESG report had a slight upward trend in positive tone one year followed by a dip the next, GPT-4o’s output showed a corresponding rise and fall in positive sentiment (however, at a somewhat elevated level overall). In fact, GPT-4o’s positive sentiment proportions were

consistently higher than the originals for most companies and years. This indicates a somewhat more upbeat phrasing, but the pattern of changes year-to-year closely mirrored the source. The same was true for negative sentiment: GPT-4o summaries captured the direction of change almost perfectly, though often with a marginally higher level of negative wording than the originals.

NotebookLM’s summaries, by contrast, tended to “flatten” sentiment variations and often skewed toward a more neutral or sanitized tone. For positive sentiment, NotebookLM generally stayed very close to the original levels (or slightly below), and in years where the original text might have become more enthusiastic or more restrained, NotebookLM’s tone showed less responsiveness to those shifts. The divergence is most striking in the negative sentiment trend, which we can see from Figure 5: while the original reports and GPT-4o maintained a consistent level of negative wording (for example, BP’s and Shell’s reports hovered around 1.5%-1.8% negative words in both 2019 and 2022, with GPT-4o summaries in a similar range), NotebookLM’s summaries dropped most of the negative content over time. In 2019, NotebookLM used roughly 1.9% negative words on average, but by 2022 this fell to about 1.1%, even though the originals did not show a comparable decrease (and GPT-4o stayed around 1.5%-1.8%).

5. Figure: Negative Sentiment Over Time by Model

Nearly halving of negative word usage by NotebookLM suggests that this model systematically omitted or rephrased negative information from the summaries as time went on. From a stakeholder perspective, such a change could be misleading, take, for instance, if a company’s later report contained admissions of challenges (negative content) that NotebookLM then downplayed or ignored, a reader of the summary might wrongly infer an improvement or a consistently positive outlook.

Another clear pattern is seen in regulatory or risk-related language, which we demonstrated in Figure 6. The original ESG reports naturally include a small proportion of litigious terms, referring to legal and regulatory language. For certain companies during the years 2020 to 2022, these terms made up about 5 percent of the total word count, with litigious word ratios reaching approximately 0.050. Both GPT-4o and NotebookLM consistently produced summaries with fewer such terms than the originals. By 2022, the average litigious word percentage in GPT-4o summaries had dropped to roughly 0.023 (2.3%) and in NotebookLM outputs to about 0.014 (1.4%), compared to ~0.05 (5%) in the original ESG reports.

6. Figure: Litigious Sentiment Over Time by Model

In other words, GPT-4o captured less than half, and NotebookLM barely one-quarter, of the regulatory risk-related content that was present in the actual reports. While the absolute differences (a few percentage points) seem small, they are large in relative terms given the low baseline frequency of such terms; the models are omitting a significant portion of the risk/compliance discourse. This finding implies that LLM summaries might underrepresent compliance, legal disclaimers, or detailed risk discussions, potentially skewing the perceived focus of the reports away from challenges and obligations. A similar effect is observed for constraining language (terms indicating constraints, requirements, or limitations). In 2019-2020, all three document types (Original, GPT-4o, NotebookLM) had roughly comparable levels of constraining words (around 5-6% of words). After 2020, however, GPT-4o's summaries showed a noticeable decline in constraining terminology (dropping from approximately 6% in 2020 to 4% in 2022), whereas the original reports remained steady around 5% and NotebookLM's use of such terms was consistently low (~4%). The GPT-4o trend suggests that in later years the model may have been paraphrasing or omitting details about constraints or requirements (e.g. omitting repeated statements of commitments, rules, or

limitations present in the original text), thereby painting a freer or less restricted picture of the company’s situation.

5.1.2. FinBERT Sentiment Analysis

To complement the word-level sentiment analysis, we also applied the FinBERT classifier (as explained in Section 4.3.2) to classify documents as positive, neutral, or negative in tone. However, to reiterate, this classifier is limited at 10,000 characters, which is the entire document in the LLM summaries in a lot of cases, but only a few pages of the ESG reports. This provides a view of how the overall sentiment of each summary compares to the original. The table below (Table 3) showcases the FinBERT sentiment distribution by model and company.

FinBERT_Sentiment	Company	Model	neutral	positive
0	BP	GPT-4o	2	3
1	BP	NotebookLM	3	2
2	BP	Original	4	1
3	Eni	GPT-4o	4	1
4	Eni	NotebookLM	4	1
5	Eni	Original	5	0
6	Equinor	GPT-4o	4	1
7	Equinor	NotebookLM	3	2
8	Equinor	Original	2	3
9	OMV	GPT-4o	5	0
10	OMV	NotebookLM	5	0
11	OMV	Original	5	0
12	Repsol	GPT-4o	2	3
13	Repsol	NotebookLM	1	4
14	Repsol	Original	4	1
15	Shell	GPT-4o	2	3
16	Shell	NotebookLM	4	1
17	Shell	Original	5	0
18	Total Energy	GPT-4o	2	3
19	Total Energy	NotebookLM	2	3
20	Total Energy	Original	4	1
21	Uniper	GPT-4o	4	1
22	Uniper	NotebookLM	3	2
23	Uniper	Original	3	2

3. Table: FinBERT sentiment distribution by model and company.

The FinBERT results indicated that the LLM-generated summaries were generally perceived as more positive than the original reports (Lu & Jagoda, 2023; Maynez et al., 2020).

Across all eight companies and five years (40 documents per type), the original reports were classified as “positive” 8 times in total, whereas the two LLMs classified 15 summaries as positive each. In other words, the AI summaries had almost double the number of positive classifications. Several companies illustrate this shift: for Shell, none of the original annual reports were classified as positive (they were all neutral according to FinBERT), yet GPT-4o’s summaries of Shell yielded 2 out of 5 years classified as positive, and NotebookLM similarly turned some Shell reports positive where the original had none. Repsol’s summaries by NotebookLM were classified as positive in 4 out of 5 years (versus only 1 year for the original), making NotebookLM’s output for Repsol the most positive leaning of any in the sample. BP, Eni, and TotalEnergies also saw both LLMs classify more of their reports as positive than were the originals. The only partial exception was Equinor: its original reports had 3 out of 5 years positive, whereas GPT-4o and NotebookLM summaries for Equinor were slightly more often neutral - suggesting that for this company, the models did not exaggerate positivity, and if anything, GPT-4o produced more tempered summaries (Equinor had more neutral classifications under LLMs than in the original). Even so, the overall cross-company tendency was clear: LLM summaries present a more upbeat picture of ESG reports, which could reflect a bias of these models to use more optimistic or PR-friendly language in summarisation.

Statistical analysis on the FinBERT classification counts found that differences in sentiment distribution across different models (Original vs GPT-4o vs NotebookLM) were not statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ (one-way ANOVA $p = 0.29$ for model effect on sentiment counts), likely due in part to the limited sample size per category and the fact that many documents were neutral in all. We displayed the ANOVA table of the results below (Table 4). However, differences by company were significant ($p \approx 0.03$), confirming that some companies (such as Repsol or Equinor) consistently exhibit more positive-toned reports than others regardless of model.

Variable	Grouping	F-statistic	p-value
FinBERT_sentiment_score	Company	2.33	0.0295
	Year	0.82	0.5175
	Model	1.9	0.1542

4. Table: ANOVA on FinBERT Score

The lack of a clear model effect in ANOVA, despite the evident patterns in totals noted above, suggests that while the models do tend to be more positive overall, the variability and small n (only 5 summary documents per model per company) make it hard to detect statistically.

Nonetheless, the directional trend is important from a practical standpoint: both GPT-4o and NotebookLM introduced an optimistic bias in summarising ESG reports, which is consistent with the reductions in negative and litigious wording noted earlier. In effect, the AI models often “softened” the tone of the documents - deliberately or not - by minimizing negativity and highlighting or inserting positive/general statements. This could mislead readers: for instance, a summary might downplay discussions of failures or risks, leading stakeholders to believe the company’s performance or outlook is more positive than the full report would indicate.

5.1.3. Summary of Sentiment Analysis

In summary, the sentiment analysis reveals that LLM-generated summaries can distort the tone of ESG disclosures. They may understate negative, risk-related, and constraining information (especially NotebookLM, which dropped a significant amount of negative and litigious content) and at times overstate positive aspects. These tonal shifts, while not as apparent as factual errors, have important implications nonetheless. An overly optimistic summary could reduce a sense of urgency that was present in the original document (for example, concerning climate transition challenges or governance issues), whereas an overly neutral summary might strip out the narrative color that indicates how a company perceives its progress. These findings align with concerns in the literature that abstractive summarisation models often are not entirely faithful to the source and can omit important details or inject subtle biases (Maynez et al., 2020). For stakeholders relying on such summaries, the risk is that they receive a filtered interpretation of the company’s ESG communication (more positive, less technical tone). Having discussed these sentiment and tone differences, we now turn to thematic content distortions identified via topic modelling, on a per-company basis.

5.2. Topic Modelling and Thematic Fidelity

In addition to tonal variation, this study investigated whether LLM-generated summaries preserve the thematic composition of original ESG reports. As we previously mentioned in Section 4.4, we identified six latent topics, enabling systematic comparison of thematic coverage across models, companies, and years. This section examines the faithfulness of topic reproduction by generative AI, the presence of topic drift, and the statistical significance of observed shifts.

5.2.1. Overview of LDA Topics

The LDA model identified six semantically coherent topics across the corpus, each corresponding to a dominant thematic focus within ESG reporting. These included:

Topic 0: Environmental strategy and emissions targets - keywords: equinor, report, financial, performance, gas, oil, energy, usd, million, annual

Topic 1: Financial disclosures and operational performance: keywords: energy, total, emissions, gas, carbon, climate, oil, strategy, scope, natural

Topic 2: Regulatory compliance and legal obligations - keywords: omv, uniper, sustainability, management, report, energy, business, emissions, employees, water

Topic 3: Social responsibility and stakeholder engagement - keywords: company, totalenergies, repsol, emissions, energy, esg, climate, gas, investors, carbon

Topic 4: Governance, internal control, and risk frameworks - keywords: shell, energy, emissions, report, gas, sustainability, million, data, tonnes, performance

Topic 5: Transition planning and future-oriented goals: - keywords: eni, bp, sustainability, energy, carbon, development, emissions, transition, local, rights

To understand which specific themes or topics were preserved or lost in the AI summaries, we employed an LDA topic model on the corpus of documents. The topic number ($k = 6$) was determined through coherence scoring, as discussed in Section 4.4.2.

While these topic labels are broad, they provide a useful framework for analyzing how each company's main messages were summarized. We next discuss each of the eight companies (BP, Eni, Equinor, OMV, Repsol, Shell, TotalEnergies, and Uniper) in turn, comparing the topic distributions of the original reports to those of the GPT-4o and NotebookLM summaries.

5.2.2. Company-Specific Findings

1. BP

BP's original ESG reports present a relatively balanced thematic distribution (Figure 7). From 2018 to 2022, the company steadily increased its emphasis on financial and operational performance (Topic 0), peaking in 2022 with extensive discussion of metrics and results. Quantitative reporting and compliance (Topic 4) remained a consistent focus point

throughout. Climate strategy (Topic 1) was especially prominent in 2018-2019, while external ESG communications (Topic 3) expanded notably in the early 2020s, reflecting increased public and investor engagement. Internal ESG management (Topic 2) was consistently present, though less dominant, and transition/social themes (Topic 5) appeared regularly without becoming central.

The summaries generated by GPT-4o and NotebookLM significantly distorted these patterns. GPT-4o underrepresented financial and compliance content (Topics 0 and 4), even in years when they dominated the original reports. For instance, in 2022, Topic 0 received virtually no emphasis in GPT-4o’s output. Both models also downplayed internal processes (Topic 2), with NotebookLM particularly overlooking operational aspects. Conversely, Topic 5 was greatly inflated (especially by GPT-4o) misrepresenting BP’s modest coverage of long-term transition and social issues as a dominant theme. GPT-4o did reflect the rise in stakeholder-oriented communication (Topic 3), but NotebookLM largely missed this shift, providing a more static portrayal.

Overall, both AI-generated summaries skew BP’s narrative toward a more aspirational, future-focused story, at the expense of the concrete performance, governance, and internal management detail that characterises the original disclosures.

7. Figure: Topic Trends over Years for BP

2. Eni

Eni's summaries demonstrate a striking thematic misalignment (Figure 8). GPT-4o attributed nearly 100% of Eni's content to Topic 2 (ESG management) across all years, despite this theme being largely absent in the original reports. This suggests GPT-4o misclassified structural or procedural language as evidence of internal ESG processes, constructing a narrative that did not exist. NotebookLM assigned virtually all content to Topic 0 (financial performance), which is equally inaccurate, as Eni's ESG sections contained minimal financial discussion. Both outputs therefore misrepresented Eni's actual emphasis, external stakeholder communication (Topic 3), which was the dominant theme throughout the original reports.

Neither model registered the brief appearances of climate strategy (Topic 1) in 2018 and 2022, nor did they reflect minor governance content (Topic 4). While both avoided injecting aspirational transition themes (Topic 5) that were absent in the original, this small accuracy is outweighed by the significant thematic distortions. A stakeholder reading only these summaries would miss Eni's key branding and messaging efforts entirely and come away with a false impression: GPT-4o implies a focus on operational processes, while NotebookLM suggests financial performance, neither of which reflects Eni's real ESG narrative.

This illustrates a breakdown in model reliability, with each AI "failing" in a different way on the same content. The result is not just a loss of nuance but an inversion of the core message, demonstrating that LLM summaries may be untrustworthy for content with specific communicative intentions like ESG reporting.

8. Figure: Topic Trends over Years for Eni

3. Equinor

Equinor’s original ESG reports from 2018 to 2022 reflect a gradual evolution across several themes, with increasing emphasis on financial and operational performance (Topic 0) and a notable rise in climate-related content (Topic 1) by 2022 (Figure 9). Other themes remained present but secondary: ESG management (Topic 2) appeared moderately through discussions of internal processes and safety; external communication (Topic 3) maintained a steady, mid-level presence; and governance/risk (Topic 4) gained attention over time. Transition/social themes (Topic 5) were minimal despite Equinor’s public positioning, suggesting either dispersed framing or a focus on concrete measures over aspirational rhetoric.

GPT-4o’s summaries failed to reflect this nuance. They consistently over-attributed Equinor’s content to Topic 2, flattening the company’s multifaceted reports into a narrow narrative of internal ESG management. This overgeneralisation missed the growing focus on finance and climate in 2021–2022, misrepresenting Equinor’s evolving priorities. In contrast, NotebookLM’s summaries fluctuated inconsistently: some years overemphasised governance (Topic 4), others external messaging (Topic 3), but without a pattern that matched the original progression. For instance, governance was exaggerated in 2020 and 2022, while climate (Topic

1) remained virtually invisible in all years, despite being increasingly relevant in Equinor’s later reports.

Neither model accurately captured Equinor’s balanced and gradually shifting strategy. GPT-4o offered a simplified and static view focused on internal systems, while NotebookLM presented a volatile narrative with abrupt and misleading shifts. Both LLMs overlooked the rise in data-driven climate discussion and improved governance reporting in 2022. These distortions risk misleading stakeholders: GPT-4o implies a narrow operational focus, and NotebookLM suggests inconsistent strategic direction, neither of which reflects reality.

9. Figure: Topic Trends over Years for Equinor

4. OMV

OMV’s original ESG reports were consistently dominated by operational ESG content (Topic 2), with a clear emphasis on internal systems, safety, and process-oriented disclosures (Figure 10). Unlike peers that focused more on climate or governance, OMV’s reports maintained a traditional, management-focused narrative. Other themes appeared only marginally: financial performance (Topic 0) and climate strategy (Topic 1) were barely mentioned, external ESG messaging (Topic 3) peaked slightly in 2018 and 2022, and governance (Topic 4) and transition themes (Topic 5) were nearly absent.

GPT-4o captured this focus well. It assigned Topic 2 a dominant share, closely mirroring the original reports, and introduced only minor distortions, slightly overstating Topics 0 and 3, but without overshadowing the primary message. In contrast, NotebookLM’s summaries were severely misaligned: it failed to detect Topic 2 entirely and instead misclassified nearly all content as governance-related (Topic 4), a theme virtually absent in the originals. This suggests a major misreading of procedural content or a parsing flaw that led to an imagined focus on governance.

Both models overlooked the modest fluctuations in climate content (Topic 1), and both slightly inflated OMV’s external messaging. Still, GPT-4o’s overall performance offers a rare example of high-fidelity summarisation, suggesting OMV’s clear, operations-heavy reporting was easier for the model to process accurately. NotebookLM, however, presented a wholly misleading picture, implying a governance focus that never existed.

OMV’s case highlights the stark contrast between model performances: while GPT-4o offered a largely accurate summary, NotebookLM’s output would leave stakeholders with a fundamentally false understanding of OMV’s ESG priorities. It underscores the importance of model reliability and the risks of relying on AI summaries without human validation—especially when model behavior can diverge so dramatically.

10. Figure: Topic Trends over Years for OMV

5. Repsol

Repsol's ESG reports from 2018 to 2022 were focusing on governance, risk, and compliance content (Topic 4), setting it apart from peers (Figure 11). Nearly all content in the original reports focused on internal control structures, audit processes, and oversight mechanisms. Other themes were minor: financial performance (Topic 0) appeared only slightly in 2022, climate strategy (Topic 1) and ESG operations (Topic 2) were virtually absent, and external messaging (Topic 3) appeared only in brief moments. Transition and social themes (Topic 5) were negligible throughout.

Both GPT-4o and NotebookLM failed to reflect this core emphasis on governance. GPT-4o misrepresented the reports as entirely focused on ESG operations (Topic 2), constructing a false narrative of process-heavy internal management. NotebookLM took the opposite approach, classifying Repsol's content almost entirely as climate strategy (Topic 1), despite the original reports containing no such focus. These distortions are especially problematic because they replace the dominant theme (governance) with content that was effectively absent, rendering the summaries substantively inaccurate.

A small point of accuracy: both models correctly reflected minor amounts of external messaging (Topic 3), aligning with brief stakeholder mentions in the original texts. Financial content was slightly picked up by GPT-4o in 2022 and mostly missed by NotebookLM.

Repsol's case highlights a critical failure in LLM summarisation when the dominant theme is technical and non-narrative. Governance content, which is dense, procedural, and often dry seems to be systematically under-recognised by both models. GPT-4o appears to assume ESG reports are about internal operations by default, while NotebookLM projects climate content even where none exists. For stakeholders, these errors could seriously distort perceptions of Repsol's strategy, wrongly suggesting a focus on climate or ESG programmes, when in fact the reports reflect a compliance-oriented governance approach. This case further highlights the need for human oversight and highlights the risk of relying on LLMs when key content lacks an easily summarised narrative structure.

11. Figure: Topic Trends over Years for Repsol

6. Shell

Shell’s ESG reports from 2018 to 2022 revealed a shift in emphasis from external communication to internal ESG management (Figure 12). In early years, Shell focused heavily on stakeholder-facing content (Topic 3), which steadily declined by 2022. In contrast, operational ESG management (Topic 2) increased sharply, peaking in 2021–2022, indicating a strategic move toward integrating ESG processes internally. Climate strategy (Topic 1) and financial performance (Topic 0) were minimal throughout, while governance (Topic 4) was present at low, stable levels. Transition and social themes (Topic 5) were virtually absent.

The LLM summaries, however, failed to capture this trajectory. GPT-4o misclassified Shell’s reports as almost entirely focused on financial performance (Topic 0), likely misinterpreting general performance terms or energy metrics. NotebookLM made the opposite error, assigning nearly 100% to external messaging (Topic 3), even as the original reports reduced that focus over time. Neither model registered the actual rise in Topic 2 content, Shell’s primary thematic shift.

Both models also introduced small inaccuracies: a slight but unjustified presence of climate content (Topic 1), and neglect of modest governance coverage (Topic 4). Transition themes (Topic 5) were accurately minimal. The result is a stark divergence: GPT-4o framed Shell’s ESG reports as financially driven, while NotebookLM portrayed them as persistently PR-heavy, both missing the company’s evolving internal focus.

Shell’s case exemplifies how LLMs can not only distort content but invert a company’s strategic narrative. GPT-4o shifted Shell’s trajectory from external to financial, while NotebookLM presented a static external narrative. These plausible sounding but incorrect summaries could mislead stakeholders if taken at face value. The inconsistencies between models reinforce the need for human oversight in interpreting AI-generated summaries of complex, evolving disclosures.

12. Figure: Topic Trends over Years for Shell

7. TotalEnergies

TotalEnergies’ ESG reports from 2018 to 2022 were heavily focused on governance and climate strategy (Topics 4 and 1), often dominating the content entirely in alternating years or sections (Figure 13). This indicates a dual emphasis; internal control structures, risk management, and compliance, alongside detailed decarbonisation and climate-related strategies. Other topics were largely absent: financial performance (Topic 0) and ESG operations (Topic 2) received almost no attention, with only a small increase in Topic 2 in 2022. External messaging (Topic 3) was minimal, with a brief spike in 2021, and transition/social themes (Topic 5) were entirely absent.

The LLM-generated summaries missed these dominant themes. GPT-4o reframed the reports around financial performance and ESG operations (two areas almost non-existent in the original reports). It portrayed a growing financial focus from 2018 to 2022 (Topic 0) and overstated internal management themes (Topic 2), fabricating an operations-heavy narrative. NotebookLM, by contrast, failed to strongly highlight any theme. Its summaries remained thematically flat, omitting the climate and governance content altogether, and offering no clear signal to the reader.

Neither model captured the reports' central message. GPT-4o misrepresented TotalEnergies' ESG disclosures, while NotebookLM offered a vague and uninformative account. Both failed to reflect the company's clear focus on climate strategy and internal governance. Notably, only GPT-4o correctly identified the small spike in external messaging in 2021 (Topic 3), a rare moment of alignment.

TotalEnergies' case highlights two distinct LLM weaknesses: GPT-4o's tendency to misframe reports around expected financial narratives, and NotebookLM's tendency to omit dominant but technical themes. This highlights a broader challenge LLMs face with technical ESG content and the importance of human validation when interpreting summarised disclosures.

13. Figure: Topic Trends over Years for TotalEnergies

8. Uniper

Uniper’s ESG reports from 2018 to 2022 were uniquely focused on a single theme: climate strategy (Topic 1), with ~100% of the content in each year devoted to decarbonisation, CO₂ targets, and emissions performance (Figure 14). All other topics were virtually absent. This made Uniper a rare case of a one-topic ESG disclosure, which, in theory, should have been straightforward for summarisation models to capture.

However, both GPT-4o and NotebookLM failed to retain this focus. GPT-4o omitted Topic 1 entirely, redistributing content across Topics 0, 3, and 4, misrepresenting the reports as containing financial, stakeholder, and governance themes that were nearly absent in the originals. NotebookLM was even more extreme, assigning nearly 100% of Uniper’s content to ESG operations (Topic 2), falsely reframing climate disclosures as internal process reporting.

The result is a complete loss of the core theme. Neither model recognised that Uniper’s reports were singularly about climate strategy, instead substituting more generic or “narrative-friendly” content. GPT-4o introduced a misleading mix, while NotebookLM created a confident but entirely incorrect one-topic summary. Even minor overstatements in Topics 3 and 4 are significant in this context, as any reference to governance or branding gives a false impression of Uniper’s priorities.

Uniper’s case is particularly troubling: it demonstrates that LLMs can fail even with highly concentrated thematic content. The inability to recognise and retain an overwhelmingly dominant theme suggests that technical ESG discussions (such as climate reporting) may be underweighted or reinterpreted inappropriately. For stakeholders relying on summaries, this leads to a dangerously misleading view: the most critical information about Uniper’s emissions and transition challenges would go unnoticed.

This case reinforces a broader finding; LLMs struggle with highly technical, non-narrative ESG content. Both models substituted other narratives in place of the actual climate strategy, demonstrating that even clear and dominant themes can be erased. Uniper exemplifies the risks of unvalidated AI summaries, particularly when they confidently distort the content of focused ESG disclosures.

14. Figure: Topic Trends over Years for Uniper

5.2.3. Cross-Company Comparison: Topic Modelling Trends and Implications

A recurring issue across companies was the complete omission of core themes from the AI summaries. Uniper, whose ESG reports were entirely focused on climate strategy and emissions (Topic 1), saw this emphasis erased in both GPT-4o and NotebookLM outputs. Similarly, TotalEnergies and Repsol both had original reports dominated by governance and risk (Topic 4), which neither model preserved. The same was true for Shell, where the growing focus on ESG operational management (Topic 2) from 2018 to 2022 was almost entirely lost in both summarisation outputs. These findings highlight the models’ consistent difficulty in capturing either highly technical (governance) or procedural (operational ESG) language, especially when not framed in a narrative style.

In contrast to omissions, some themes were exaggerated or misclassified. GPT-4o frequently overrepresented Topic 0 (financial performance), as seen in its summaries of Shell, TotalEnergies and Equinor. These companies’ original reports did not centre on profitability or operational metrics, yet the summaries reframed their ESG content through a financial lens. By comparison, NotebookLM repeatedly misclassified content as Topic 2 (operational ESG), most notably in its summaries of Uniper, OMV and Eni, despite these companies placing limited emphasis on process language in their source material. Another pattern was inflated external ESG framing (Topic 3) in summaries, particularly from NotebookLM, which often misread generic sustainability statements as investor-oriented or reputational narratives.

Some companies experienced better alignment than others. OMV was the only firm where GPT-4o captured the dominant theme (Topic 2: ESG operations) with relative accuracy. By contrast, Repsol and Shell were both cases of critical thematic breakdown, where the summaries diverged entirely from the structure and emphasis of the originals. BP, while not immune to distortion, showed more stable thematic profiles across all three document types. This suggests that companies with more standardised or less complex reporting structures, like BP and OMV, may be less susceptible to severe model drift.

Another key insight is that AI summaries, especially those by NotebookLM, fail to reflect thematic changes over time. For instance, Equinor's increased emphasis on financial and environmental topics (Topics 0 and 1) in 2022 is captured in the original reports but remains flat or misaligned in the summaries. Similarly, Shell's growing attention to operational ESG was completely missed. This flattening effect means that LLM-generated summaries may not only misrepresent the overall structure of a report but also its evolution, concealing a company's actual progress or strategic shifts over time.

Across all companies, GPT-4o tended to produce summaries that emphasised financial or managerial content, often regardless of the source material's actual focus. NotebookLM, by contrast, leaned toward generic ESG framing, frequently missing key themes while overstating external communication or compliance. Notably, neither model consistently captured climate strategy (Topic 1) well, which is especially concerning given that this is often the most prominent ESG issue for energy companies. These patterns suggest that the underlying training and prompting mechanisms of each model influence not only tone but also what content is extracted and highlighted.

These findings have serious implications for stakeholders relying on LLM-generated ESG summaries. First, the thematic drift introduced by the models can mislead investors, regulators or the public about what a company is actually saying. A reader may come away believing that a firm is focused on financial performance or stakeholder engagement when its primary emphasis was compliance or risk. Second, model dependence creates reproducibility issues. Two models summarising the same report can yield entirely different narratives, raising questions about consistency, transparency and fairness in automated ESG communication. Finally, the tendency of both models to flatten or ignore year-on-year thematic change means they are ill-suited for tracking ESG progress or regressions over time.

In sum, while large language models can capture the general gist of ESG reports, they fail to preserve the thematic nuance that gives those disclosures meaning. Their output should be treated as a filtered interpretation rather than a faithful distillation. Human oversight remains essential; not only for accuracy, but also for ensuring that AI-generated summaries do not distort the very sustainability values they are meant to communicate.

5.2.4 Cross-Model Comparison

In comparing GPT-4o and NotebookLM across all companies, it becomes clear that while both models fall short of fully faithful thematic reproduction, they do so in notably different ways. Both AI summarizers exhibit significant departures from the original ESG reports' topic distributions (as confirmed by statistical tests indicating model type as a significant factor). In general, neither model consistently preserves the exact thematic balance of the source material - yet the distortions introduced by each are distinct, reflecting underlying model-specific biases. This comparative view highlights consistent trends of omission and exaggeration, as well as divergences in how each model reinterprets content, ultimately affecting the fidelity of the summaries.

A striking common pattern is that both GPT-4o and NotebookLM often failed to retain the core themes of the original reports whenever a company's disclosure was dominated by a particular topic. If an ESG report concentrated heavily on a single issue (for instance, climate strategy, regulatory compliance, or governance) that central focus tended to vanish from both models' summaries. The models struggled especially with content that was highly technical or non-narrative, such as detailed governance protocols or internal process descriptions, frequently omitting these less "story-like" themes entirely. For example, TotalEnergies' and Repsol's originals were largely centered on governance and risk management (Topic 4), yet that emphasis disappeared in both the GPT-4o and NotebookLM summaries. Another case is that Shell's increasing focus on operational ESG management (Topic 2) over the years was almost completely missed by both models. In such cases, neither AI system identified and preserved what was arguably the most important topic, underscoring a broad weakness in thematic fidelity when faced with a strongly focused source.

Even more apparent, is the case of a one-theme report like Uniper's. Uniper's ESG reports were almost entirely devoted to climate strategy and emissions (essentially a single dominant theme, Topic 1), which in theory should be straightforward for a summary to capture.

Yet both GPT-4o and NotebookLM failed to capture this focus: each model’s summary effectively erased the climate topic altogether. GPT-4o’s version omitted any mention of the climate strategy and instead redistributed Uniper’s content across unrelated themes, introducing spurious references to financial performance, stakeholder engagement, and even governance matters that were nearly absent in the original text. NotebookLM’s output was, in a different way, just as misleading: it assigned almost 100% of Uniper’s summary content to an “ESG operations” topic (Topic 2), essentially hallucinating an internal-process narrative that did not exist in the source material. In other words, GPT-4o fabricated a mix of minor themes as substitutes, while NotebookLM reframed the entire report into the wrong theme. This example illustrates the general risk that even an overwhelmingly dominant topic can be omitted or replaced by the generative models, leaving the summary unfaithful to the original emphasis. Consistently across the evaluated companies, whenever a report placed singular importance on a particular issue (be it climate, governance, or another specialized domain), the AI summaries proved unreliable in reflecting that priority. Both models showed a tendency to underweight highly focused, technical content.

Despite these common omissions, GPT-4o and NotebookLM differed in how they reframed and biased the content that was included. GPT-4o had a tendency to cast ESG information through a financial or managerial lens, often highlighting profitability, production, or high-level strategy even when those were not central in the source material. In practice, GPT-4o’s summaries frequently overrepresented Topic 0 (financial performance and operational metrics). For example, in summarizing Shell, TotalEnergies, and Equinor, GPT-4o had a disproportionate focus on financial results and business outcomes, despite those companies’ ESG reports not being centered on profit or revenue at all. This suggests that GPT-4o instinctively highlights business performance themes, skewing the summary toward managerial “success” narratives, likely due to its training on a broad corpus of corporate and financial texts. By contrast, NotebookLM tended to lean toward generic ESG framing and internal process topics. It often misclassified or reconceived content as Topic 2 (operational ESG management and compliance) even when the original report put little emphasis on internal procedures. The result was that NotebookLM’s summaries sometimes read like procedural checklists, focusing on compliance and internal initiatives instead of the source’s real focus. For instance, NotebookLM’s summaries of companies such as OMV and Eni framed the content as internal ESG operations and policies, despite those companies not heavily stressing such themes in their reports. Similarly, NotebookLM inflated external communication themes

(Topic 3), often interpreting neutral or generic sustainability statements as investor- or stakeholder-oriented messages. In short, NotebookLM displays a bias toward viewing the material as either internal process or public-facing rhetoric, even when unwarranted, which is a contrast to GPT-4o’s bias toward financial and strategic highlights.

These model-specific distortions mean that each AI tends to overstate certain topics and neglect others in a consistent way. GPT-4o, with its business-oriented filter, was more likely to overemphasize financial performance or growth aspects, potentially at the expense of ESG details. NotebookLM, on the other hand, often overstated procedural or public-relations aspects, while glossing over concrete specifics unique to the company, for example, giving undue weight to compliance measures or broad commitments. Some important themes were downplayed by both models. Environmental and climate issues were not reliably highlighted even when they were a central theme in the original reports. Governance and risk-related content tended to be underrepresented across the board, aligning with the observed drop in negative or cautionary language in the summaries. Both AI systems preferred upbeat, narratively convenient topics, which meant that risk, compliance, and other themes received less attention or were paraphrased into milder terms.

This reflects the optimistic bias in thematic terms, as well in semantics (discussed in Section 5.1). An example is that discussions of regulatory challenges or liabilities (typically classified under governance/risk topics) were not only linguistically toned down but also thematically marginalized in the summaries. In effect, if a company’s report dealt with uncomfortable truths or technical details, both GPT-4o and NotebookLM were prone to either omit those aspects or replace them with more palatable content. The difference lies in how the two LLMs present it. GPT-4o might fill the space with something it deemed relevant (even if misplaced, such as emphasizing financial stability or general “ESG progress”), whereas NotebookLM might simply leave a thematic void or default to generic statements. Neither approach delivers a faithful portrayal of the source material’s priorities.

The cross-model differences also extend to how consistently each model performs across different companies. In the aggregate, statistical analysis (ANOVA) confirms that model choice significantly affected the topic distribution of the summaries, with both models deviating in their own ways from the originals ($p < 0.01$ for the model effect in topic coverage, according to the ANOVA). In other words, GPT-4o and NotebookLM each introduce their own pattern of thematic distortion, and these patterns were robust enough to be detected as

systematic differences rather than random variance. Notably, the analysis did not find either model to be categorically “better” across all topics, both had relative strengths and weaknesses. GPT-4o occasionally captured a key theme that NotebookLM missed: OMV was the one company where GPT-4o actually preserved the dominant topic (ESG operations) with reasonable accuracy, however, an isolated success. In many other cases (e.g. Repsol or Shell), both models experienced complete thematic breakdowns, failing to mirror the structure or emphasis of the original reports at all. On balance, GPT-4o’s summaries tended to be more content-rich but inclined to confident mischaracterization, whereas NotebookLM’s summaries were often overly generalized, missing the nuance of the source that an expert would pick up on. These tendencies meant that across the set of companies, GPT-4o might give a reader the impression of a more financially focused, optimistic report than actually written, while NotebookLM might yield a blander account that obscures key issues behind generic ESG verbiage.

Circling back to our first research question, yes (in Section 2), AI-generated summaries without a doubt exhibit bias, both in tone and especially in content selection relative to the original reports.

5.3. Quantitative Deviation Analysis

Building on the earlier textual and thematic analysis, this section investigates whether LLM-generated ESG summaries reproduce key environmental metrics accurately. The goal is to assess whether these AI-generated summaries reflect the original data or introduce factual distortions. It goes beyond just measuring average errors, it also considers the direction and consistency of mistakes, categorizes them by severity, and identifies trends in over- or under-reporting. By looking at median values, interquartile ranges (IQR), and error bands, the analysis offers a clear and structured view of each model’s reliability. This helps highlight which ESG metrics are most often misrepresented and whether there are systematic flaws in how these models handle factual content.

5.3.1. Average Deviation Across Sources

We calculated both the average absolute and percentage deviations from the original ESG figures to set a baseline for the reliability of the ESG summaries. As Figure 15 shows, the results point to clear differences between the models. GPT-4o had the highest average

percentage deviation at 72%, followed by Eikon at 46%, NotebookLM at 19%, and Bloomberg at just 3%. At first, this suggests GPT-4o underperforms compared to both NotebookLM and third-party benchmarks. However, these headline figures hide the fact that accuracy varies widely across different firms and metrics.

15 Figure: Average deviation by source (GPT-4o, NotebookLM, Bloomberg, Eikon) benchmarked against original ESG disclosures.

5.3.2. Firm-Level Variation

When categorized by company, we see a broader picture. GPT-4o’s performance varied a lot across firms, with Equinor and Uniper showing particularly high mean percentage deviations (226% and 159%, respectively). These likely reflect the challenges GPT-4o faces with unusually formatted or complex ESG disclosures. In contrast, GPT-4o tended to under-report values for companies like Shell (-17%), Repsol (-52%), and OMV (-45%), which may be due to conservative summarization or omission of (see Appendix Table A1 for company-wise deviation percentages).

NotebookLM, on the other hand, showed much more consistent results, typically maintaining deviations in the low double digits. For example, its average deviations were just 12% for Eni, 14% for Equinor, and 3% for TotalEnergies. However, it significantly overestimated BP’s values, with a 100% average deviation. This shows that even the more stable model (quantitatively) has notable blind spots.

These results show substantial firm-level inconsistencies. A model that performs well on one report may struggle with another, depending on formatting, terminology, or structure.

In some cases, such as Equinor or Uniper, GPT-4o may have misinterpreted data, leading to exaggerated or misleading outputs. Meanwhile, despite its stable average performance, NotebookLM still struggled with specific cases, notably overestimating BP’s data. As illustrated in Figure 16, these firm-level differences reveal the uneven performance of both LLMs across the investigated companies.

16 Figure: Firm-level average deviation by model, showing variability across companies.

Metric-Specific Challenges

Analyzing deviations by metric reveals that certain ESG indicators consistently challenge LLMs, especially those that are inconsistently reported or presented in ambiguous formats.

GPT-4o exhibited its largest average error on “waste generated,” where the mean percentage deviation reached an overwhelming 621%. This either shows hallucinated values or misinterpretations of units (e.g., tonnes vs. kilotonnes). It also significantly overestimated Green CapEx (237%) and under-reported Scope 3 emissions (-39%), suggesting either omission or misreading of figures.

NotebookLM performed better overall but still struggled with specific metrics. Its average deviation for Scope 2 emissions was +68% and +25% for Scope 3. Green CapEx also presented difficulties (+21%), though not to the same extent as GPT-4o. Notably, NotebookLM’s deviation for water withdrawal was +13%, compared to GPT-4o’s -42%, hinting at fewer hallucinations or more conservative results.

These patterns suggest that Scope 3 emissions and investment-related metrics are harder to interpret accurately and more often reported incorrectly. In contrast, Scope 1 and 2 emissions saw lower deviation across both models, likely due to how obviously they feature in ESG disclosures and in an established and standard format. Figure 17 below illustrates the variation in average deviation by metric across both models, while the underlying data is detailed in Appendix Table A2.

17 Figure: Metric-level average deviation by model across six environmental KPIs.

5.3.3. Benchmarking Against Third-Party ESG Sources

To better understand the performance of the AI models, we benchmarked GPT-4o and NotebookLM not only against the original ESG reports but also against trusted third-party providers, Bloomberg and Eikon. Bloomberg’s average deviation from original ESG disclosures was just 3%, suggesting near-perfect alignment. Eikon, while less precise, had a deviation of 46%, still within an expected range due to possible methodological adjustments.

When comparing AI outputs directly to these sources, the gaps become clearer. As shown in Figure 18 GPT-4o deviated by an average of 111% from Bloomberg and 112% from Eikon, which reinforces its struggle with numerical consistency. NotebookLM, in contrast, had smaller gaps 31% from Bloomberg and 20% from Eikon. This places NotebookLM’s summaries closer to third-party figures.

18 Figure: Average deviation of models from Bloomberg and Eikon third-party ESG data.

5.3.4. Median and Inter-Quartile Range Analysis

The analysis of model performance in the context of ESG data shows a major statistical distinction, the mean, while useful for flagging major discrepancies, is highly sensitive to outliers and can exaggerate a model’s overall inaccuracy. This sensitivity is evident in GPT-4o’s performance, where its average deviation of 72% was heavily influenced by extreme overestimations in certain metrics, such as waste generated (621%) and green capital expenditure (237%). As a result, the high mean obscures the fact that many of GPT-4o’s outputs were much closer to the true values. To get a clearer and more representative picture of typical model behavior, it’s more useful to rely on summary statistics that are less affected by outliers, specifically the median and interquartile range (IQR). Table 5 contains the median and IQR for each model, which highlights the sharp contrast between GPT-4o’s volatile output and NotebookLM’s tighter, more consistent range of deviations.

	GPT-4o	NotebookLM
Average Deviation (Median)	-3%	0%
Interquartile Range (Q3-Q1)	65%	4%

5 Table: Median deviation and interquartile range (IQR) for GPT-4o and NotebookLM.

The median, a more reliable indicator of central tendency, pinpoints the midpoint of all deviations and, unlike the mean, remains unaffected by extreme values. This makes it a more reliable indicator of typical model performance. When looking at median percentage deviations

from the original ESG figures, a very different picture emerges compared to the mean. GPT-4o, for example, has a median deviation of just -3%, a significant shift from its 72% mean, suggesting that most of its results were much closer to the true values than the average implies. NotebookLM performs even better, with a median deviation of 0%, indicating strong alignment with the original data for most of its outputs. This gap between the mean and median highlights how a few large errors, such as inflated CapEx or emissions estimates skew the average but don't reflect typical performance.

However, the median alone doesn't tell the whole story. To better understand how consistent a model is, we also need to consider the spread of its deviations and this is where the interquartile range (IQR) becomes essential. IQR represents the spread of the middle 50% of the data, effectively indicating the consistency and reliability of a model's outputs. GPT-4o has a wide IQR of 65%, meaning that half of its outputs deviated by more than $\pm 32.5\%$ from the actual figures. This level of dispersion indicates significant inconsistency, even if the median appears low. In contrast, NotebookLM's IQR is just 4%, reflecting much tighter clustering around the true values and significantly more consistent performance.

This pattern also holds when comparing the models against third-party ESG sources like Bloomberg and Eikon. As shown in Figure 19, GPT-4o has a median deviation of 0% from both sources, but its IQRs of 130% versus Bloomberg and 106% versus Eikon, suggest extreme volatility, making its individual outputs highly unpredictable. NotebookLM again shows greater stability, with IQRs of 21% and 25% respectively. While not perfect, these are far narrower than GPT-4o's, supporting the conclusion that NotebookLM delivers more consistent and dependable ESG figures when measured against industry benchmarks.

19 Figure: Median deviation and IQR of model outputs compared to Bloomberg and Eikon benchmarks.

5.3.5. Metric-Level Median and IQR Deviation Patterns

To better understand the source of these differences, we break down the median and IQR values by individual ESG metric. This helps identify which types of disclosures are mostly distorted. The results in Figure 20 (Median Deviations) and Figure 21 (IQRs) reveal a clear difference in model behavior at the metric level.

20 Figure: Metric-level median deviations across models showing directional tendencies.

21 Figure: Interquartile ranges by ESG metric, illustrating consistency of each model.

GPT-4o’s deviations are both more erratic and more extreme. For example, it overstates waste generated by a median of 424% with an IQR of 379%, indicating wild variability in that metric. Similarly, for Green CapEx (median: +21%, IQR: 278%) and Scope 2 emissions (median: –25%, IQR: 119%) how substantial swings and a lack of directional consistency. These patterns suggest that GPT-4o struggles most with metrics that are often buried in complex narrative sections or presented ambiguously in ESG reports.

NotebookLM, on the other hand, shows much better consistency across all six environmental metrics. Its median deviation is 0% for every metric except Scope 2 (30%), and its IQR values remain extremely narrow, as low as 0% for Scope 3, CapEx, and Water Withdrawal, and peaking at just 52% for Scope 2. This consistency suggests a more reliable extraction process that avoids hallucinations and handles difficult-to-locate data more effectively. A full breakdown of median and IQR values by ESG metric is available in Appendix Table A3.

Taken together, the combined analysis of mean, median, and interquartile range offers a well-rounded picture of the factual reliability of each model. GPT-4o appears to be highly inconsistent, while its median deviations indicate that many results are close to the actual values, its wide IQRs and inflated means reveal frequent, severe outliers. NotebookLM, on the other hand, shows stronger alignment with original disclosures and third-party benchmarks but also maintains tight IQRs, reflecting more stable and accurate outputs overall. While no model is entirely error-free, these results point to a clear difference in performance: NotebookLM

offers more dependable factual reproductions, whereas GPT-4o’s output often requires closer inspection due to its tendency toward volatility and exaggeration.

However, numerical accuracy is not just about average error sizes, it also involves understanding the practical effects of those errors. A model that frequently produces small deviations may still be considered trustworthy, while one that occasionally generates large, misleading figures might be more problematic, even if its average performance appears acceptable. To evaluate this, we complement our earlier statistical analysis with a qualitative classification of error size. By grouping deviations into low, moderate, and high bands based on established materiality thresholds (see Section 4.6.5) we can better assess how often each model produces outputs that would be considered acceptable, questionable, or misleading in real-world ESG contexts. The next section applies this framework to compare the factual levels of errors across GPT-4o and NotebookLM.

5.3.6. Error Band Classification Results

As discussed previously in the methodology section, to translate raw numerical deviations into a more natural form, we classified each AI-generated value into one of three error bands: “low” ($\leq 5\%$), “moderate” (5–20%), and “high” ($> 20\%$).

When comparing overall performance, NotebookLM performed slightly better, with 77.1% of its outputs falling within the low deviation band, compared to 68.7% for GPT-4o. NotebookLM also had slightly fewer high-deviation outputs (18.1%) than GPT-4o (22.9%), while medium deviations were relatively rare in both models (4.8% for NotebookLM vs. 8.4% for GPT-4o). Although NotebookLM displayed somewhat stronger consistency, the difference is not stark, both models followed broadly similar deviation patterns and neither was entirely free from significant errors (see Figure 22).

22 Figure: Share of low ($\leq 5\%$), moderate (5–20%), and high ($> 20\%$) deviations across models.

However, breaking the results down by specific ESG metrics reveals more variation in how each model handled different types of data. However, breaking the results down by specific ESG metrics reveals more variation in how each model handled different types of data. For Scope 1 emissions, both models performed well. Nearly all outputs were in the low deviation range, with just one high deviation each, reflecting the relative clarity and frequency of this metric in ESG reports. In contrast, Scope 2 emissions proved more difficult for both models. GPT-4o had 7 out of 17 values in the high deviation band (41%), NotebookLM performed slightly worse, with 8 out of 14 (57%) in the same category. This suggests that Scope 2 data which tends to be less standardized and more variable across firms is more prone to extraction errors.

In other areas, differences become clearer. Waste generated was one of GPT-4o’s weakest metrics, with 5 out of 7 values (71%) deviating by more than 20%, whereas NotebookLM had just 1 high deviation out of 9. Similarly, GPT-4o struggled with Green CapEx, returning high deviations in 6 of its 11 values (55%), compared to 3 of 13 (23%) for NotebookLM. These gaps suggest that GPT-4o may be more sensitive to errors in metrics involving areas where format inconsistencies and unit ambiguity are common. On the other hand, both models performed strongly on Water withdrawal and Scope 3 emissions, with most values falling in the low deviation band. Notably, GPT-4o returned no high deviations for Scope 3 or Water Withdrawal, though it did have a few medium-range errors, while NotebookLM had just one high deviation in each case.

Overall, while NotebookLM shows a slightly more stable pattern, particularly in reducing medium and high deviations, the difference is not too noticeable. Both models performed well on standardized metrics but struggled in areas where numerical data may be more complex, such as Scope 2 emissions and Green CapEx. A detailed breakdown of model performance across each ESG metric and deviation band is provided in Appendix Table A4.

However, these all the statistics discussed above were direction-neutral, they revealed how large the deviations were, but not whether the models tended to overstate or understate the reported figures. The next part of the analysis addresses this gap by examining the direction of error, focusing on patterns of over- and under-reporting. This shifts the focus from factual accuracy to potential narrative bias, linking back to earlier findings from the textual analysis where tone and sentiment also varied between models.

5.3.7. Directional Bias: Patterns of Over- and Under-Reporting

While the previous sections assessed the scale and consistency of AI-generated ESG deviations, they did not yet consider the direction of these deviations. In practice, whether a model overstates or understates sustainability metrics can significantly influence stakeholder perception just as much as the size of the error itself.

This issue closely parallels the sentiment distortion discussed in the textual analysis earlier in the thesis. (Section There, GPT-4o was found to downplay negative language, often softening tone in ways that cast companies in a more favorable light. A similar concern arises in the quantitative domain, if a model consistently inflates metrics like green CapEx or deflates emissions figures, it may reinforce or even amplify overly optimistic narratives in the original reports. Conversely, under-reporting of achievements could hide genuine progress and mislead risk-averse investors.

To assess whether factual errors have a pattern rather than random variance, we analyzed the direction of each deviation, categorizing model outputs as overstated, understated, or perfectly matched relative to the original reported values. This analysis allows us to assess whether errors are randomly distributed or skewed in a particular direction.

The results show a clear difference between the two models. GPT-4o had a strong tendency to under-report, with 48 out of 84 values (57%) falling below the original figures, compared to 31 overstatements. Only 4 values (5%) matched the originals exactly. This pattern

suggests that GPT-4o may often miss or misinterpret values during summarization. When paired with its high rate of large deviations, this tendency could distort how a company’s performance is judged.

NotebookLM, in contrast, was far more balanced and accurate. Out of 84 values, 37 (44%) were exact matches, which is something GPT-4o did not come close to achieving. The rest were nearly evenly split between overstatements (24) and understatements (22), showing no clear directional bias. This suggests that NotebookLM’s deviations are more likely to be random or context-dependent, rather than a systematic narrative bias. These results are summarized visually in Figure 23, which shows how the two models differ in the directional breakdown of their factual errors.

23 Figure: Directional bias: Counts of over-, under-, and exact matches by model.

5.3.8. Metric-Level Patterns

Breaking down the over- and under-reporting by ESG metric helps show which types of indicators each model finds more difficult to identify, and how those difficulties appear in their outputs. For GPT-4o, the clearest pattern is a strong tendency to under-report emissions across all scopes. It under-reported Scope 1 emissions in 18 out of 25 cases (72%), Scope 2 in 9 cases (~22%), and Scope 3 in 12 (25%), while achieving no perfect match on any of these. This suggests that GPT-4o has difficulty locating or correctly interpreting emissions data especially when the numbers are buried in dense text or presented with different units. Its consistent under-reporting in these categories could leave readers with an overly optimistic impression of a company’s climate performance.

However, GPT-4o showed a more mixed pattern on investment-related and operational metrics. It over-reported green CapEx in 8 out of 11 cases (~73%), suggesting stronger environmental efforts, despite those figures more loosely mentioned or ambiguously presented. Similarly, it over-reported waste generated in 5 out of 7 cases (~71%), but significantly under-reported water withdrawal (7 out of 10), indicating inconsistent behavior on resource-related disclosures.

On the other hand, NotebookLM showed far better accuracy and balance across all categories. It achieved perfect matches in 11 of 23 Scope 1 cases (~48%), 8 of 13 Scope 3 cases (~62%), and 10 of 13 green CapEx cases (~77%). While it did slightly over-report Scope 1 and Scope 2 emissions in a few instances (7 and 8 respectively), nearly balanced out by under-reporting, suggesting no clear directional bias. Overall, its high number of exact matches and more even distribution of deviations point to a more reliable and nuanced understanding of the numerical context.

Overall, these metric-level results support the broader patterns discussed in Section 5.3. GPT-4o tends to consistently under-report emissions and shows mixed behaviour across other areas, whereas NotebookLM generally delivers more accurate facts and remains neutral in tone. For stakeholders who rely on ESG summaries to guide risk assessments or investment decisions, these differences are important. They affect not only how accurate the numbers are, but also whether the summaries present a consistently optimistic or pessimistic picture. A full breakdown of overreported, underreported, and accurately reported values by ESG metric and model is provided in Appendix Table A5.

5.3.9. Missing and Fabricated Values: Omissions and Hallucinations

Other than measuring how far AI-generated ESG values deviate from the original, another key concern is whether the models leave out important figures or include numbers that were never reported at all. These kinds of errors, known as omissions and hallucinations, represent the most serious form of factual inaccuracy. In such cases, models either overlook available data or invent numbers entirely, both of which can mislead stakeholders in ways that are difficult to catch without manual verification. We can see this summarized in Table 6, which compares the total number of omissions and hallucinations for each model.

	GPT-4o	NotebookLM
Not reported	83	83
Hallucinations	23	7

6 Table: Total omissions and hallucinations by model across all ESG metrics.

Across the dataset, GPT-4o and NotebookLM each failed to report 83 ESG figures that were present in the original disclosures. These omissions were most frequent in waste generated, Scope 2 emissions, and Scope 3 emissions. These metrics are often buried in narrative sections or expressed in non-standard formats. For instance, GPT-4o failed to report waste figures in 20 instances, and Scope 3 emissions in 17, highlighting challenges in extracting data that’s not presented in tabular or clearly structured form. NotebookLM showed a similar pattern, with 18 omissions in waste and Scope 2, and 17 in Scope 3, confirming that both models struggle with metrics that lack standard placement or formatting across reports. A more detailed breakdown is presented in Figure 24, highlighting which categories were most frequently skipped by each model.

24 Figure: Number of missing (unreported) ESG values by metric for each model.

The two models show a clear difference in hallucinated content. GPT-4o hallucinated 23 values (instances where it presented a number that did not exist in the original ESG report). These mostly appeared in areas like green CapEx or water withdrawal, where the original text contained qualitative references but no actual numbers. NotebookLM, by contrast, only hallucinated 7 values, suggesting a far more cautious approach when information was ambiguous or missing entirely. This pattern supports the conclusion that GPT-4o tends to fill in gaps more aggressively, while NotebookLM is more likely to acknowledge uncertainty or leave values unreported.

These results highlight an important aspect of factual reliability that standard deviation metrics cannot fully capture. Omissions impact the completeness of a summary, while hallucinations undermine its credibility and both can significantly distort how a company's ESG performance is understood. For users relying on AI-generated summaries, these types of errors are particularly serious, especially when they're hard to spot.

5.3.10. Conclusion of Quantitative Analysis

The quantitative deviation analysis presented in this section offers a comprehensive assessment of the numerical reliability of AI-generated ESG summaries. By examining deviations in magnitude, direction, and frequency across models, firms, and environmental metrics, the analysis reveals clear differences in factual consistency between GPT-4o and NotebookLM. While GPT-4o showed strong median accuracy, its wide interquartile ranges, high average deviations, and frequent hallucinations point to a tendency to often misleading outputs. This volatility, especially in metrics such as waste generated and Scope 2 emissions, raises concerns about its reliability in contexts where numerical precision is essential.

In contrast, NotebookLM consistently outperformed GPT-4o across almost all tests. With tighter IQRs, more values in the low-deviation band, and a notably high number of exact matches, it proved to be the more precise and stable model. Its balanced pattern of over- and under-reporting, along with fewer hallucinations, reinforces its credibility when it comes to accurately capturing ESG data. That said, both models struggled with less standardized metrics like Scope 3 emissions and qualitative CapEx disclosures, highlighting shared limitations when data is presented in ambiguous or unstructured formats.

This analysis also makes it clear that numerical deviation alone isn't enough to evaluate the quality of AI-generated outputs. Directional bias, missing data, hallucinated values, and overall consistency across companies and ESG categories are all important factors. While NotebookLM stands out as the more reliable of the two, neither model is flawless, and both are still capable of producing errors that could mislead users or misrepresent a company's true sustainability performance.

6. Summary of Results

This section summarizes the textual and quantitative findings to assess whether AI-generated ESG summaries can faithfully replicate original reports. The results show that while LLMs can capture general ESG content, they frequently distort tone, thematic focus, and factual data. These issues often overlap, collectively affecting the reliability of the summaries. Together, the findings directly address RQ1, RQ2, and RQ3. (Section 2)

Regarding RQ1, we see consistent tonal and thematic bias in summaries produced by GPT-4o and NotebookLM. Lexicon-based sentiment analysis revealed that AI summaries systematically showed a more positive picture of the companies. This occurred not through a significantly higher use of positive language, but by downplaying regulatory and risk-related terms, which is the primary way companies communicate “threats” and “weaknesses”. The ability to read between the lines is a trait of expert analysts, but current LLMs do not appear to possess this skill. Topic modelling further exposed how both models altered the thematic focus of reports. For instance, Uniper’s strong emphasis on climate strategy was entirely absent in both GPT-4o and NotebookLM summaries. In several other cases, governance and risk themes were downplayed or lost, while the models focused on minor or unrelated topics. Shell’s increasing focus on operational ESG improvements over time was also not captured by either model. These results confirm that the models often fail to preserve the primary focus of a report, especially when it is highly technical or narrowly framed.

The models also reframe content in systematic ways. GPT-4o leaned toward financial and strategic themes, often emphasizing profit-related language even when not central in the original reports. NotebookLM, in contrast, overrepresented procedural ESG content and external communications. These biases remained consistent across different firms and years, showing limited responsiveness to company-specific or time-based variation.

RQ3 concerns factual accuracy, particularly of numerical data. Here, GPT-4o exhibited high error rates, with average deviations of 72% across six environmental metrics. Errors were sometimes extreme, including a 600% deviation for “waste generated” and 237% for Green CapEx. NotebookLM was more reliable, with average deviations closer to 19% and notably accurate reproduction of some metrics like Scope 1 emissions and waste. However, it also introduced meaningful overestimations for Scope 2 and Scope 3 emissions.

For RQ2, benchmarking AI outputs against third-party ESG data providers shows that GPT-4o deviates by over 110% from Bloomberg and Eikon figures, while NotebookLM stays within 20 to 30%. GPT-4o performed particularly poorly for firms like Equinor and Uniper, where hallucinated values and omissions were common. NotebookLM was more consistent across firms, with lower variability in error but still produced substantial deviations for select cases, such as BP.

In summary, these findings confirm that current AI models often alter both the tone and content of ESG disclosures, with significant variation depending on the theme, company, and data type. While NotebookLM outperforms GPT-4o in both consistency and accuracy, neither model can be relied upon to fully preserve the narrative or numerical integrity of original ESG reports. These results form the basis for the implications discussed in the next section.

6.1 Implications for ESG Integrity

Thematic drift and tonal bias in AI-generated ESG summaries pose a serious threat to stakeholder trust, transparency, and accountability. When governance, legal, or risk content is downplayed and aspirational language amplified, summaries may falsely suggest progress or responsibility (Lu and Jagoda, 2023, Bingler et al., 2024). This distortion is not just stylistic, it influences how investors, regulators, and the public perceive a firm's sustainability, affecting capital allocation, compliance, and reputation (Christensen et al., 2021).

Our findings show that these narrative shifts often align with numerical inaccuracies. Upbeat summaries frequently under-reported emissions, especially Scope 3, or overstated green investments like Green CapEx. In some cases, figures were entirely hallucinated, such as GPT-4o's "waste generated" values with deviations exceeding 600 percent. These combined distortions in tone and data present serious credibility risks. Prior research has shown that LLMs can produce confident, yet incorrect, technical summaries (Ni et al., 2023, Kryściński et al., 2020), underscoring the importance of scrutiny in ESG contexts.

The deviation between GPT-4o and NotebookLM shows that both thematic and factual accuracy depend on the model. GPT-4o often emphasized financial themes regardless of source emphasis, while NotebookLM focused more on compliance and procedures. This inconsistency points to a broader issue of non-reproducibility in AI summarization (Dremel et al., 2017, Yadav and Bethard, 2018), which limits standardization and comparability.

These risks raise important regulatory and ethical concerns. AI summaries may give an overly favorable view of a company's sustainability, omitting key risks or caveats. This aligns with Binger et al.'s (2024) concept of "greenwashing by machine," where AI unintentionally amplifies vague or misleading narratives. To reduce these risks, human oversight, verification, and regulatory guidance are essential. Hybrid approaches, where AI supports but experts review summaries, offer a viable interim solution (Haribhakti and Sridharan, 2024, Runyon and Warren, 2024). Auditable and traceable tools, such as ChatReport (Ni et al., 2023), can also help increase transparency and accountability.

In conclusion, while LLMs improve efficiency in ESG reporting, they are not yet reliable as standalone tools. Until issues of bias, error, and reproducibility are addressed, AI summaries should remain supplementary, not a replacement for source-based, verified reporting.

7. Limitations

While the study offers valuable insights, several limitations should be noted. First, the scope was narrow, focusing on a small sample of large firms within one industry over a limited time span. This restricts the generalizability of the findings across sectors, company sizes, and longer periods. Data availability was another constraint: of roughly 1,200 expected values, only 396 could be analyzed due to incomplete disclosures and inconsistencies in ESG reporting. Metrics were often poorly labeled, hard to locate, or reported in incompatible formats. Moreover, some AI-generated summaries hallucinated figures or omitted numerical data entirely, introducing potential noise and reducing the sample for comparison.

The analysis also involved subjective decisions. For example, topic modelling required manual interpretation of themes, and assigning topics to texts involved judgment calls, making full replication challenging. The LDA model itself, while useful, simplified complex content into six broad topics and may have missed important sub-themes. Sentiment analysis, too, had methodological constraints: the Loughran-McDonald lexicon lacks contextual depth, and FinBERT was limited to the first 10,000 characters of each text, potentially missing sentiment shifts in longer reports.

Additionally, the findings depend on two specific AI models, GPT-4o and NotebookLM, as they functioned at the time of study. Their behavior may not reflect other models or future updates. For instance, GPT-4o showed more variability in numeric outputs, while NotebookLM was more consistent. Since these models operate as black boxes and were used with zero-shot prompts, some summarization errors may be prompt- or model-specific. Finally, the study did not include human evaluation of the summaries, so the real-world impact on reader understanding or trust remains untested.

Despite these limitations in sample size, data quality, subjectivity, and model choice, the research presents a structured, in-depth analysis of how LLMs handle ESG reporting, highlighting both their potential and their current shortcomings.

8. Recommendations for Further Research

A natural next step is to expand the analysis to include more companies, industries, and years. A larger and more diverse sample across sectors and regions would help determine if the observed patterns are consistent or specific to this sample. It could also highlight sector differences, such as how AI handles reports from tech firms compared to oil companies, improving the general relevance of the findings.

Although this study focused on two advanced language models, the field is evolving quickly. Future research should evaluate a wider range of models, including open access, commercial, and specialized tools. This could clarify whether issues like sentiment bias or missing governance details vary by model or are common across different systems.

Future studies could also test whether more tailored prompts or few-shot examples improve accuracy and reduce bias. For example, guiding the model to “highlight governance issues” may reduce thematic omissions. Comparing these approaches with our base case could show how prompt design influences summary quality and provide practical advice on how organizations can improve AI outputs through simple prompt engineering.

A major limitation was the manual extraction of values. Future work could use automated methods such as optical character recognition, entity detection, or ESG-focused language tools to collect data more efficiently. Using standard datasets like GRI or CSRD could also increase consistency and allow for larger studies.

Beyond sentiment and topic analysis, future research could assess readability and writing style. Metrics like Flesch-Kincaid scores, jargon frequency, and sentence variety could uncover subtler differences between human and AI writing. This would show whether AI simplifies or overcomplicates material and how such changes affect stakeholder understanding. Style analysis could add depth to our understanding of AI’s communication impact.

Finally, applied research could test how LLMs can be responsibly integrated into corporate reporting. Pilot programs with real companies could evaluate time savings, required human oversight, and stakeholder responses. These trials could lead to practical guidelines e.g., requiring human review for risk sections or including disclaimers for AI-generated content. Involving regulators could also help develop standards for safe and transparent AI use in disclosures, ensuring real-world benefits from academic insights.

9. AI Statement

In the course of this thesis, we have used AI tools to support various stages of the research and writing process. Specifically, we used OpenAI's GPT-4o and Google's NotebookLM to assist with:

- Generating the summaries of ESG reports for comparative analysis.
- Rephrasing and translating text to ensure clarity and consistency.
- Providing coding support in Python for data processing, sentiment analysis, and topic modeling.
- Offering suggestions for structuring thoughts and improving the flow of arguments.
- Contributing ideas to connect different analytical components in a cohesive manner.

All AI-generated outputs were critically reviewed, revised, and validated by us to ensure academic integrity and compliance with ethical research standards. The use of AI did not replace our own analysis, interpretation, or writing, but served as a complementary tool to enhance the quality and efficiency of our work.

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Appendix

All supplementary data, code and AI-generated summaries are available at <https://10.5281/zenodo.15532966>.

Appendix A – Supplementary Quantitative Results

Table A1. Firm-level Average Deviation Percentages

This table presents the average percentage deviations between AI-generated ESG summary values and the original reported values, aggregated at the firm level. Positive values indicate overestimation, and negative values indicate underestimation by the model.

Firm	GPT-4o	NotebookLM
BP	13%	100%
Eni	81%	12%
Equinor	226%	14%
OMV	-45%	-4%
Repsol	-52%	0%
Shell	-17%	-3%
Total Energies	1%	3%
Uniper	159%	28%

Table A2. Metric-specific Average Deviations

This table reports the average deviation in reported values for key environmental performance metrics, comparing the AI-generated summaries to the source data.

Metric	GPT-4o	NotebookLM
Scope 1 Emissions	-12%	-5%
Scope 2 Emissions	17%	68%
Scope 3 Emissions	-39%	25%
Waste Generated	621%	0%
Water Withdrawal	-42%	13%
Green Capex	237%	21%

Table A3. Median and IQR by ESG Metric

This table shows the median deviation and interquartile range (IQR) of deviations for each metric, offering insights into both central tendency and variability of the errors.

Metric	GPT-4o Median	GPT-4o IQR	NotebookLM Median	NotebookLM IQR
Scope 1 Emissions	-3%	17%	0%	3%
Scope 2 Emissions	-25%	119%	30%	52%
Scope 3 Emissions	-41%	48%	0%	0%
Waste Generated	424%	379%	0%	14%
Water Withdrawal	-63%	76%	0%	1%
Green Capex	21%	278%	0%	0%

Table A4. Error Band Classification by Metric

This table categorizes the absolute deviation for each metric and model into three bands: Low (<5%), Medium (5–20%), and High (>20%).

Metric	GPT-4o Low	GPT-4o Medium	GPT-4o High	NotebookLM Low	NotebookLM Medium	NotebookLM High
Scope 1 Emissions	20	4	1	19	3	1
Scope 2 Emissions	10	0	7	6	0	8
Scope 3 Emissions	13	0	0	11	1	1
Waste Generated	2	0	5	8	0	1
Water Withdrawal	8	2	0	10	0	1
Green Capex	4	1	6	10	0	3

Table A5. Directional Bias Classification by Metric

This table shows whether each model tended to overstate, understate, or exactly match the original values for each metric.

Metric	GPT-4o Over	GPT-4o Under	GPT-4o Perfect	NotebookLM Over	NotebookLM Under	NotebookLM Perfect
Scope 1 Emissions	7	18	0	7	5	11
Scope 2 Emissions	7	9	1	8	4	2
Scope 3 Emissions	1	12	0	2	3	8
Waste Generated	5	1	1	1	4	4
Water Withdrawal	3	7	0	3	6	2
Green Capex	8	1	2	3	0	10